

HiLCoE School of
Computer Science & Technology

A LOCALIZED PORTAL FOR THE
DEVELOPMENT OF MAILING, RECRUITMENT,
AND YELLOW PAGE APPLICATION IN 4
DIFFERENT LANGUAGES

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Part 1

Project Proposal

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of the Internet in the late 1990s led to explosive growth in exchange of information and services over the World Wide Web.

addisportal.com is a web based portal system designed by accommodating three different services into one. These services are mailing, jobs searching and yellow page.

The portal system that is going to be developed will have one foreign and three local languages, which are English, Amharic, Oromifa and Tigrigna

The availability of these three web services in to one gives any user to get different service by just accessing a single web site. This project is initiated by the group members considering that most people have been isolated from accessing these facilities due to lack of languages skill.

1.1. Background

The reason that initiates the group to develop the localized portal system is that it is hard to find these three services into one using local language. So by developing the portal system problems of most local peoples toward using foreign languages could be resolved.

1.2. Overview of the problem

There are no enough efficient systems that address the issue of mailing and yellow pages and job search service specially using the stated local languages.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In our fast growing and developing globalize world using local languages on any Information Technology systems boost the interest of local language users towards using computer systems, and it could give satisfaction to the user. The main problem of using services that are provided using foreign language is lack of language skill. Therefore localizing computer system could increase interaction within the society and it could lead in to over all development of the nation.

For Mailing Service

- What has been attempted so far is only using Amharic language and it has not been done for the rest of local languages.

For Yellow Pages

- Difficulty to locate different service providers.
- Tour guides are restricted to normal business operating hours.
- Difficult on conducting using local languages.

For Job Search

- Difficulty in communicating a job seeker with an employer.
- Difficult on posting and accessing positions in local languages

Above all the availability of these three systems into one using local languages has not been done so far.

3. OBJECTIVES

3.1. General Objectives

The general objective of this project is to develop an automated web based system which incorporates E-mail, job search and yellow page services.

3.2. Specific Objectives

List of major activities to meet the general objectives are:

The problems that will be addressed are:-

- Designing a system that incorporate three services
- Enable the system to function using local languages beside English.

4. SCOPE AND LIMITATION

E-mail Service Scope

- It serve text and the service of attaching files
- the system gives the services using four different languages

Limitation

- It doesn't provide mail span
- It doesn't provide address book service
- It will not provide file attachment

Job Search Service Scope

- It provides vacancy announcement service
- The system will function using three local languages

Limitation

- Placement of employees for the posted position will not be discussed

Yellow Page Service Scope

- Browse Directory contains different service providers.
- The service will be provided using different local language options

Limitation

- The yellow page will only considered locations and services in Addis Ababa

5. TOOLS & METHODOLOGY

5.1. Data collection Methodology

- Previously done senior project document analysis [mail and chat provider,2005], [localization on open office,2006]
- Similar site observations like www.yahoo.com and so on.
- Interview

5.2. System Development Methodology

In the system development methodology we have tried to compare and make decision in the two basic approaches. Structured approach and Object Oriented approach.

Structured approach: Is used to map the problem domain to flows and transformation. It is more on function oriented.

Object oriented approach: is based on the concept of object.

We choose Object Oriented analysis approach. The reason for choosing Object Oriented methodology over long standing structured approach is based on the benefits linked with object oriented approach which includes Information hiding, Modularity, Data abstraction, Inheritance and Polymorphism.

Object oriented system, structuring programs into objects offers conceptual simplicity, promoting ease of understanding, which improves requirements capture, documentation and maintenance. Encapsulation of data and method produces a modularity, which localized the effects of changes. The inheritance mechanism combined with polymorphism and dynamic binding allows reused objects to be tailored to fit a new application.

5.3. Implementation

Since the object oriented methodology will be used throughout the project, we will use different design tools associated with the methodology.

We have divided the design tools into two major categories based on the system's design view, as the dynamic view and static view of the system.

- Under the dynamic view of the system, we will use sequence diagram, use case diagram, collaboration diagram, state chart diagram, activity diagram, and

- Under the static view of the system, we will use the class diagram, object diagram, component diagram and deployment diagram as appropriate

The following programming tools will be applied in order to implement the project

- Rational Rose
- Macromedia Dreamweaver
- Apache or Internet Information Service
- Microsoft Windows Server 2000 or 2003
- Visual Basic 2005
- Microsoft SQL Server

- MySQL
- Microsoft Windows XP
- Microsoft office
- Ulead Photo Impact
- Adobe Photoshop
- And others

6. SIGNIFICANCE

Interactivity: - yellow page users who needs to search place or services, job seekers and mail user are engaged in dialogue that dynamically advertises the experience to the individual and makes the yellow page users, job seekers, and mail users a co-participant in the process of exchange.

Being able to give service 24 x 7 x 365:- The system can operate all day every day. Your physical storefront does not need to be open in order to obtain service.

Opportunity to reduce costs: - Since the services are going to be available on the internet it would reduce the overall costs. For example employer could easily void paper based expenses for vacancy announcement.

7. BENEFICIARIES

Over all being web system itself enables the user to access it from anywhere so that yellow-page users could search for whatever they might need while any job seeker could easily being informed without paying a visit of requesting a position in any organization. Above all it could lead any one to get the service because it could be provided using local languages.

In General our system could benefit local peoples on using the indicated service since it is going to be developed using local languages.

8. SCHEDULE

8.1. Work Breakdown Structure

- 0.0 addisportal.com
- 1.0 Problem identification
- 2.0 Analysis
 - 2.1 Business area analysis
 - 2.1.1 Problem Identifying
 - 2.1.1.1 Internal Factors
 - 2.1.1.2 External Factors
 - 2.1.2 Identifying Refined business class diagram
Strength of the current system
 - 2.2 Requirement definition
 - 2.2.1 Identify functional requirement
 - 2.2.2 Identify non functional requirement
- 3.0 Design
 - 3.1 System use case
 - 3.1.1 UI Identification
 - 3.1.2 Business Rule Identification
 - 3.1.3 Actor Identification
 - 3.1.4 Designing the use case diagram
 - 3.1.5 Use case description
 - 3.2 Sequence diagramming
 - 3.2.1 Unrefined class diagram
 - 3.2.2 Class decomposition
 - 3.2.3 Refined business class diagram
 - 3.3 Conceptual modeling
 - 3.4 Activity diagram
 - 3.5 User interface prototyping
- 4.0 Conclusion

8.2. Gantt Chart

Part 2

Requirement Analysis Document (RAD)

1. INTRODUCTION

In developing country like Ethiopia there is no doubt that one has to utilize natural, social and cultural resources to alleviate poverty. Using local languages is one of the common tools to enable movement of peoples towards the policy and strategy of growth of the country. Also it's likely to import either by the governmental and private companies either capital goods or other technological advancements for local consumption. In order to utilize those imported capital goods and technological advancements it's quite relevant to prepare guides and other related operational books using local languages, to fasten growth in socio and economic affairs of the country.

Information Technology is one of the technological advancement that should be brought to local peoples using local languages. Especially in country like Ethiopia, where more than 80 languages spoken in the fourteen regions, it's a must to localize different information technology outputs into local languages to encourage peoples to bring themselves to the technology than to wait the technology to come to them.

Addisportal.com is a portal localized system that tries to provide job searching, yellow page and mailing service. In fact addisportal.com will try to provide the service by using one foreign language which is, English and three local languages which are **Oromifa**, **Tigrigna** along with **Amharic**.

Portal System

A website that serves as a gateway to the Internet. Portal is a collection of links, content, and services designed to guide users to information they are likely to find interesting news, entertainment, weather, commerce sites, chat room and so on.

Web Portal

A web portal is a site that provides a single function via a web page or site. Web portals often function as a point of access to information on the World Wide Web. Portals present information from diverse sources in a unified way. Aside from the search engine standard, web portals offer other services such as e-mail, news, stock prices, infotainment and various other features. Portals provide a way for enterprises to provide a consistent look and feel with access control and procedures for multiple applications, which otherwise would have been different entities altogether. An example of a web portal is Yahoo!.

Two broad categorizations of portals are Horizontal portals (e.g. Yahoo) and Vertical portals focused on one functional area, e.g. salesforce.com. Our system will be categorized under horizontal portal since it integrates more than one functional area.

Why portal?

It is often necessary to have a centralized application that has access to various other applications within the same enterprise to share the information across the applications. Also the various users with different roles accessing the different applications prefer to have a single access point to all of them over the Internet. They like to personalize the applications and have the coupled applications coordinated. Above all, the administrator users like to have administrative tools all in a single place to administer all the applications. All these are achieved through portals. Since all the applications share information through portals, there is better communication between various types of users. Another advantage of portals is that they can make event-driven campaigns. Below is detailed list of advantages of using portals:

- Intelligent integration and access to enterprise content, applications and processes

- Improved communication and collaboration among customers, partners, and employees
- Unified, real-time access to information held in disparate systems
- Personalized user modification and maintenance of the website presentation

Localization

Localization means taking an internationalized product and customizing it for a specific market.[senior project, localization on open office,2006:3] This includes translating the software strings, rearranging the User Interface components to preserve the original look.

For instance, if a local language speaker, who doesn't know how to speak or read English language, and wants to use a computer he/she will face a big problem since most of the computer features are in English language. So this is where localization plays a major role in changing those features to local languages.

Addisportal.com is portal system that gives mailing and job searching services along with yellow page by four different languages. There are different websites that gives the above service in the World Wide Web, but the thing that makes our system unique besides being localized is that the system is going to be developed addressing problems of the three local language speakers i.e. (Amharic, Oromifa, and Tigrigna).

1.1. Purpose of the System

In today's competitive world ICT become the order of the day and plays a dominant role in our daily activity. The purpose of our system is to provide a portal website service in four different languages. The system will be developed, especially for those who speak local languages. As it is known there are different websites that gives mailing, yellow pages and job searching services, unfortunately it is hardly useful for local language speaker because of that

most of local peoples are quite strange for foreign languages and evidently most of issues to be posted and hosted by the system may only consider the life style, tradition and social interaction of the people who lives in the country where the system is designed, and this could severely damage the interest of local people on using these systems. Above all the content of these systems could cause social disorder since the social interaction culture and traditions are different from one nation to the other. When this project is completed and implemented those local language speakers will benefit a lot. It will minimize the Language barrier for most of local people, social disorder is hardly to be happened and it enhances communications and information exchange between the societies.

1.2 Scope of the System

The system is concerned with functional units that are related with the portal system. Accordingly we have identified main functional units that are related with the system. The scope of the project will cover the basic three major services these are Mailing service, job searching services and yellow pages. Each one of these major services has their own scope.

Addis Mail Service

The mail service will provide a means for anyone to communicate using one of the indicated local languages without making a lot of effort. Under the mailing service the following will be performed:

1. Able to register new user to the web mailing system
2. Once the user registered can log into the system and have the ability of reading mail, and sending mail.
3. Able to send and read messages using English, Amharic, Oromifa and Tigrigna languages.

Addis Job Service

The job searching is going to be a means for job seeker to look for a job while it is going to be equivalently useful for the employer to look for a qualified candidate. Under the job searching service the following will be performed:

1. Job Seekers (Registered or Unregistered) can view list of vacancies
2. Able to register Employer to the system
3. Registered Employer can post vacancies
4. It provides vacancy announcement services
5. Registered employer can view the list of registered jobseekers
6. The system will be implementing in four different languages.

Addis Yellow page Service

The yellow pages is going to be a means for anyone who is looking for service providers and attractions and under this service the following will be undertaken.

1. Viewing different information about different topics
2. Holds different links to other websites
3. Provide searching service
4. The system will be implementing in four different languages

1.3 Objectives and Success Criteria of the Project

In the age of globalization information exchange becomes determinant on deciding the growth of one society in all aspects. In the mean time information exchange could require security because it becomes obvious that information is power. Unless one finds a better means to exchanging information it is quite difficult to share the benefits with the others from the global market and to bring socio economic development.

Internet has known becoming one means of exchanging information in a faster and relatively secured manner. To get a share over such advantages of Internet web based application has to be developed. By implementing web

based application and by utilizing it over the Internet, the problems mentioned in the above paragraph could be resolved.

A localized portal system will contain three services that are going to be implemented using one international and three local languages. Those three services are mailing, job searching and yellow pages services.

Motivation for doing the project is that we have interviewed a dozen of students and some Internet users from local Internet cafés and they all gave us an opinion that it would have been much easier and exciting if they are able to mail and look for a job on the Internet by their local language.

Finally our main success area aims at enabling our society, whether they are here or abroad, to easily communicate using the Internet technology without language barrier.

1.3.1 Success Criteria

Addis Mail Service

1. Anyone could send and reads mails using four languages.

Addis Job Service

1. The job seeker could easily view vacancies.
2. The employers could post and recruits job seekers easily.
3. Employer can easily view registered job seekers profile
4. The service will be provided using multiple local languages.

Addis Yellow page Service

1. The yellow-page user could get information easily.
2. Service providers easily advertise their services.
3. The service will be provided by multiple local languages.

1.4 Definition, Acronyms, and Abbreviation

Architecture: the organizational structure and associated behavior of the system.

DB: Database

IT: Information Technology

RAD: Requirement Analysis Document

UC: use case

ETC: Ethiopian Telecommunications Corporation

1.5 References

- Bruegge B. and Dutoit A. Object-Oriented Software Engineering, Conquering Complex and Changing System, Pearson Education, 2002.
- Localization on open office, a senior project from the library of HiLCoE.
- Mail and Chat Provider, a senior Project from the library of HiLCoE.
- Review of existing system e.g. yahoo.com, hotmail.com
- www.wikipedia.org
- www.enspiretech.com

2. Current System

Currently on the Internet there is quite large number of Portal system. The most common one that have been chosen by most people is www.yahoo.com that provides mailing, job searching and yellow page service.

Taking into consideration, yahoo.com in order to use the mail service the user has to register and create account. After registration is completed the user can receive mails, and send mails. These mail providers actually provide other related services.

ethiojobs.net could be consider as a good example regarding job searching system and in order to get the job search service, the job seeker and the employer has to register on the system so as to get the require facility. After the registration is completed the job seeker can view vacancies while the Employer will be given a privilege so as to post vacancies.

Regarding the yellow page Once again yahoo.com could be taken as a good example.

Different links that represent different services, infrastructures will be available so that the user could select one.

What could be considered as problem of existing system is that all of the indicated services from the mentioned service providers are being served using foreign languages and in fact it becomes a huge obstacle for most local peoples to get a facility of the World Wide Web.

3. Propose System

3.1 Overview

In general our system will consist of the following parts:

- Addis Mail
- Addis Jobs
- Addis Yellow page

The mailing service will enable anyone to create an account and to access the account using user name and password. The user will be given a privilege to read, compose and send mails using the mentioned four languages.

The job searching system will enable anyone who is interested to register as a job seeker or as an employer. The system also lets unregistered jobseekers to view list of vacancies, but only registered job seekers profiled will be viewed by the employer.

The yellow-page system will display different information and important links concerning Addis Ababa, the main aim of this system is to give information and introduce different service providers reside in Addis Ababa.

3.2 Functional Requirement

Addisportal.com is a web based portal system that gives mailing, job searching and yellow-page services that uses four different languages.

Addis Mail

Under the mailing service the following major functional areas will be addressed:

- User Registration
- Sending mail and file attachment
- Receiving mail
- Maintaining address book
- Changing language options

The mail provider will have the option to let the user to log into the system, if the user is already registered. However for the new user the system has an option to facilitate so that the user can register and access the system herewith. Once registration completed, every time to get the service the system will asks to enter username and password to give/hinder privilege. If username and password is correct, the system redirect to the page that displays the current inbox content. In this page it will show the sender name, and title of the message. In order to read the message click on the title of the message and on the next page the message will be displayed.

The other option of this system is the service of composing message. There will be a button called COMPOSE. Once you click the button, on the next page you will get the option to enter the title of the message, address of the receiver and a text area to write the body of the message. After writing the whole message, you can click the SEND button and automatically sends your messages and confirms on the next page. The confirmation can be the success of the information transmission or failure with a small description why it failed.

It has also a language option, there will be a button or a link called AMHARIC, OROMIFA, and TIGRIGNA. Once you click on one of them, the system will let to write the body of the message on the selected language.

Addis Jobs

Under the job searching service the following major functional areas will be addressed:

- Employer and Job Seeker Registration
- Browse vacancy list and post vacancy
- Changing language options

The Job search provider will have the option to let the user to log into the system if the user already a registered user. However for the new user the system has an option to facilitate so that the user can register and access the

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system herewith. Once registration completed, every time to get the service the system will asks to enter username and password to give/hinder privilege. Eventually if the user doesn't want to register he/she can just view list of vacancies. In this system there are two types of user:

1. Job Seeker
2. Employer

In the homepage there will be a registration option, under this option there are two links called JOB SEEKER and EMPLOYER. Once the user clicks each links there will be a page with a registration form (the content of the form varies) and after the user fills the form, he/she clicks the Submit button and the system automatically registers to the database and confirms the user whether the registration was successful or not. The registration can be done using four languages.

The other option of this system is the language option service. There will be a button or a link called AMHARIC, OROMIFA, and TIGRIGNA. Once you click on one of them, the entire functionalities will be provided using the selected language.

Addis Yellow page

Under the yellow page service the following major functional area will be addressed:

- Browsing Directory
- Searching service providers

The yellow-page service will let the user to view different information within Addis Ababa. In order to get the service of the system, the system doesn't ask user to register. On the official addisportal website there will be a link called ADDIS YELLOW-PAGE. Once the user clicks the link, the system automatically displays the yellow-page homepage. In the homepage there will be different links and list of available service providers in Addis Ababa. These service providers are like hotels, schools, college, universities, and hospitals

...and attractions. Every time a user clicks the link, there will be other page to display the information about that page.

The other option of this system is the language option service. There will be a button or a link called AMHARIC, OROMIFA, and TIGRIGNA. Once the clicks one of them, the system will display a homepage by the selected language.

3.3 Non Functional Requirement

3.3.1 User Interface

In general the system will have a web based interface for all services to be provided by the system.

Since one of the objectives of localizing a system is to enable the user to interact with the system by their native languages easily it is highly considered to be user friendly. Initially the first page will contain links that could lead the users to the main services that are going to be provided by the system along with a language option that the user may select. In addition news and general information will be posted on the home page.

If the user select the link that could lead him/her to either mail or job searching services of the system they will be asked by the system to log in if they have already created an account or if they do not have a user account they will be asked to register.

Here questions will be simple, personal and not hard to answer. Once logged in they will have a facility to view where the mail comes from and title for the mail from the senders. Eventually the users of the system will not have much burden to understand and proceed to whatever level they want to go.

3.3.2 Performance Characteristics

In our mail, job search and yellow pages system performance matters. The system will have intuitive and friendly interface. Performance characteristics of a system include response time, acceptability, number of concurrent access and peak hour handling. This portal system robust has taken it to account all the problems that might be attributed the above. The technology this system is going to be built up on is a robust one that has a tool to handle those problems. Hardware and software are selected based on making this system an efficient performance.

In the mail service it should enable and let users is informed whether information is sent correctly or not. This should be one of the critical aspects while designing our system.

The other part of the system where performance character is critical is on the job search and yellow pages. Unless employers get a response with shorter period of time (This mainly depends on the connection speed provided by ETC) about a qualified job seeker and if the job seeker couldn't view when ever positions are available that could meet the job seeker qualification it could be as system failure. In the same manner one should get the result of the search key on the yellow page while look for some services. Therefore this issue is very critical

Our system is going to be highly Concurrent .In the case of mail provider thousand of concurrent users can log into their web mail address and can read/write any information. Our mail server will be synchronized and designed to accept as much as thousands of users all at once.

In the case of job seeker thousand of job seekers could obtain the information at the same time and thousand of employers can access either a single individual or group of job seekers profile.

In the same manner on our yellow page thousand of peoples will be privilege to search for services and access further information at a time

therefore it is sure that high consideration should be given while designing the system in terms of concurrency.

Finally on the performance characteristics the issues of extreme or load conditions should be taken in to consideration. Certainly nothing is durable or at some point the system is susceptible to extreme conditions.

Some of them are:

- When the number of concurrent users are too many and it exceeds the bandwidth allocated from server.
- When the system detects that there is no Amharic software like Power Geez
- When the server is down with some malicious factors like virus, worms because since it will be designed and implemented client/server environment those factors will certainly hinder the flow of information.

3.3.3 Error Handling and Extreme condition

A mechanism to handle error should be employed. An error which is made by the user should not be reacted with some extreme annoying messages but a means where to inform and solve the users' problem.

In general all errors that are encountered can be commented and solved. In fact most of the errors can be easily solved. These kinds of errors are made by the users. Some of them are entering incorrect user name and password, failing to write the address of the receiver in the proper manner and other related errors can be handled and prompt the user to correct it.

Unfortunately, there are worst case scenarios here it will be impossible to trace and propose a remedy for some errors encountered, such might be

- Attack of malicious viruses or worms
- Failure of hard ware like server machines
- Failure of PC

Those kind of errors are hard to debug or impossible to propose a solution unless otherwise the system is restarted or restore again.

3.3.4 Quality Issue

Speaking of quality our system intends to have three issues which needed to be included. How reliable, available and robust the system is. Reliability in our case refers to how secure the product should be. Indeed the main concern here is security, we will see in detail how security is going to be implemented in the upcoming section while we discuss security issues. Unless it come to be clear that any users information is secured personal privacy will be invaded and questioned. Therefore the question of reliability is the utmost concern while we design our system.

Next is availability, Like that of security, if our system couldn't be accessed at any time once again it could be questioned. Availability could be easily expressed the accessibility of the system 24 x 7 x 365. Considering the service type to be provided like mail and yellow pages has to be available at any time .over all one of the strongest benefits that could be raised while talking about web based applications are the availability of the system at any time.

Robustness refers to whether our system can survive many hamper situations. This specifically refers to our mail, job searching and yellow pages server. The server should be robust enough to handle the flow and request of information.

3.3.5 System Modification

Once started, tested and run on the local machine we plan to register a domain name and lease a server to enable users around the globe, especially Ethiopian communities, to use our system. We certainly know that to provide requires a lot of space and resources. Besides current mail providers like yahoo And Google provide up to 2GB of space for free. Therefore, if we plan to make it public we need to compete with all of these providers. However, we will enable Amharic mail services which will not be provided by other providers. In future we also plan to add mote languages on the system.

3.3.6 Physical Environment

The system will be deployed on the server machines. The web server will be deployed on central server where every browser routes through.

3.3.7 Security Issue

What so ever technological innovation or advancement any one comes through if it is not secured it's out of consideration of being used. As we tried to mention about security while discussing quality issue on the service to be given by addisportal.com security issues has been given a big taught. Particularly when the user tries to access either mail or job search part of our system the user will be required to authenticate on the first page to be displayed. The system runs certain process that will confirm whether the user name and password are correct or not. Any user should not be allowed to proceeds to the next page without first passing security clearance. It happens habitually that users leave their page after login by their user name and it's obvious that another user gets difficulty in accessing or browsing using different user name, therefore we need to find a means where the page expires.

There will be critical and confidential inquiries where users are requested to fill so as to uniquely identify them. Even from our server point of view and our database need to be designed to be able to open by the administrator who is responsible to make any modification. The database also shouldn't be accessible to any person who has access to the server computer.

3.3.8 Resource Issue

Mainly the resource of the system will be web server for web page administration. We need to be online to access the information, need to have Amharic software along with the normal ones so as to compose message in Amharic also sine Tigrigna shares the same character with that of Amharic the software will also be use for messaging in Tigrigna.

3.4 System Model

3.4.1 Scenarios

Name of Scenario	Create Mail Account
Participating Actor Event flow	Solomon: mail user 1. On the addisportal homepage the user clicks the registration link. 2. The system displays a registration form. 3. Solomon enters personal information and submits the page. 4. The system checks whether the entered username is being used or not. 5. If the username is not being used, the system registers the Solomon's profile to the database 6. If it is being used, the system lets Solomon to enter other username.
Name of Scenario	Browse inbox
Participating Actor	Melaku: Mail User
Event flow	1. Melaku Clicks on Addismail link on addisportal homepage. 2. The system displays Addis mail homepage 3. Melaku enters the username and password 4. The system checks whether the entered username and password is available on the database or not 5. If it is available, the system displays the browse Inbox page.

Name of Scenario	Compose Message
Participating Actor	Meron: Mail User
Event Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Meron log in to the system and Clicks on compose button. 2. The system displays the Compose Message page 3. Meron enters Address of Receiver, Title of the Document and the Body of the document. 4. The system checks the Address of Receiver 5. If the address is available, the system sends the message and confirms the Meron that the message is delivered. If the Receiver address is not available, the system confirms Meron to re-enter the receiver Address.
Name of Scenario	Manage the system
Participating Actor	Tibebe: Addis mail service Administrator
Flow of Event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tibebe Login to the system 2. The system displays the main

page, Tibebe can perform Administrative task.

Name of Scenario	Login
Participating Actor	Mulugeta: Mail user
Event Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Mulugeta Clicks login from the homepage of Addis mail.2. Mulugeta enters username and password.3. The system will check and give/hinder privilege to the Mulugeta.
Name of Scenario	Create Employer Account
Participating Actor	Biruk: Employer
Event flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. On the addisjobs homepage Biruk clicks the employer registration link.2. The system displays a registration form.3. Biruk enters personal information and submits the page.4. The system checks whether the entered username is being used or not.5. If the username is not being used, the system registers the Biruk's profile to the database6. If it is being used, the system lets Biruk to enter other username.

Name of Scenario	Create Job Seeker Account
Participating Actor	Yonas: Job seeker
Event flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On the addisjobs homepage Yonas clicks the registration link. 2. The system displays a registration form. 3. Yonas enters personal information and submits the page. 4. The system checks whether the entered username is being used or not. 5. If the username is not being used, the system registers the yonas's profile to the database 6. If it is being used, the system lets Yonas to enter other username.
Name of Scenario	Login
Participating Actor	Biruk: Employer
Event Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Biruk Clicks login from the homepage of Addis jobs. 2. Biruk enters username and password. 3. The system will check and give/hinder privilege to the Biruk.
Name of Scenario	Login
Participating Actor	Yonas: Job seeker
Event Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Yonas Clicks log in from the homepage of Addis mail. 2. Yonas enters username and password. 3. The system will check and give/hinder

privilege to the Yonas.

Name of Scenario	Post Vacancy
Participating Actor	Biruk: Employer
Event Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Biruk login to the system2. Biruk clicks Post Vacancy button.3. The system displays a vacancy registration form4. Biruk enters the description of the vacancy5. The system will automatically register the vacancy to the database.
Name of Scenario	Browse Vacancy
participating Actor	Yonas: Job seeker
Flow of event	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. on addisjob homepage, Yonas clicks lists of vacancy link2. Yonas will click on Lists of vacancy link3. The system automatically displays lists of vacancy
Name of Scenario	Manage the system
Participating Actor	Demeke: Job search service Administrator
Flow of Event	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Demeke Login to the system2. The system displays the main page, Demeke can perform Administrative task.

Name of Scenario	Change language for mail service
Participating Actor	<p data-bbox="789 268 1081 300">Samson :mail user</p> <ol data-bbox="740 323 1430 583" style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="740 323 1360 359">1. Samson log to Addis mail home page. <li data-bbox="740 380 1430 470">2. The user clicks on one of the language option. <li data-bbox="740 491 1430 583">3. The system automatically displays the next page by the selected language.
Name of Scenario	Change language for job search service
Participating Actor	<p data-bbox="789 772 1198 804">Aster: employer/jobseeker</p>
Flow of event	<ol data-bbox="740 844 1430 1104" style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="740 844 1312 879">1. Aster log to Addis jobs home page. <li data-bbox="740 900 1430 991">2. The user clicks on one of the language option. <li data-bbox="740 1012 1430 1104">3. The system automatically displays the next page by the selected language

3.4.2 Use case Model

3.4.3 Use case Description

Use case Name	Create User Account
Description	This use case lets user to register to the system
Participating Actor	Any user who want to use the mailing or job searching service.
Pre-condition	None
Event flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1.On the addisportal homepage the user clicks the registration link2. The system displays a registration form3. The user enters the proper information4. The system checks whether the entered username is being used or not.5.If the username is not being used, the system registers the user profile to the database6. If it is being used, the system lets the user to enter other username.
Exit Condition	If registration completed or the user abort from registration form.
Special Requirement	None
Use case Name	Browse inbox
Description	Email user can view inbox message
Participating Actor	Mail User
Pre-condition	The user has to login to the system

Event flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On the Addis Mail homepage the user enters username and password. 2. The system checks whether the user name and password is available in the database or not. 3. If it is available, the system displays the browse inbox page.
Exit Condition	User Log out from the system.
Special Requirement	None
Use case Name	Compose Message
Description	Lets user to send the text message.
Participating Actor	Mail User
Pre-condition	The user must login to the system
Event Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.The user clicks the Compose button 2. The system displays the Compose Message page 3. The user enters Address of Receiver, Title of the Document and the Body of the document. 4. The system checks the Address of Receiver 5. If the address is available, the system sends the message and confirms the user that the message is delivered. 6. If the Receiver address is not available, the system confirms the user to re-enter the Receiver Address.

Exit Condition	Sending Message Successfully, failure of sending message, or user clicks Log out button
Special Requirement	None
Use case Name	
Description	This use case Lets the employer register list of vacancies to the database
Participating Actor	Employer
Pre-condition	The Employer must login to the system
Event Flow	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user clicks Post Vacancy button. 2. The system displays a vacancy registration form 3. The employer enters the description of the vacancy 4. The system will automatically register the vacancy to the database.
Exit Condition	Registration Completed or Employer exit from Registration.
Special Requirement	None
Use case Name	
Browse Vacancy	
Description	Lets job seeker to view list of vacancy
participating Actor	Job seeker
Pre-condition	None
Flow of event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Job seeker will click on Lists of vacancy link 2. The system automatically displays lists

	of vacancy
Exit Condition	When the user exit from the system
Special Requirement	None
Use case Name	Delete message
Description	This use case lets the mail user to Delete his/her message.
Participating Actor	Mail user
Pre-condition	The user must login to the system
Flow of Event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user clicks on delete button after check on the message. 2. The system will automatically remove the message.
Exit condition	Deleting message successfully or user log out
Special requirement	None
Use case Name	Manage the system
Description	A feature that is used to enhance the service of the website
Participating Actor	Administrator
Pre-condition	The Administrator Login to the system.
Flow of Event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. After authenticating the user, the system displays the main page, that the user can perform Administrative task.
Exit condition	Administrative task completed or the administrator log out.
Special requirement	None

Use case Name	Change language
Description	Lets user to change languages to Amharic, Oromifa, and Tigrigna.
Participating Actor	Mail user, Employer or job seeker
Pre-condition	None
Flow of event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system displays addisportal home page. 2. The user clicks on Amharic, Oromifa, and Tigrigna link based on his/her choice. 3.The system automatically display the next page on the selected language
Exit Condition	Changing language performed successfully
Special Requirement	None
Use case Name	Login
Description	This use case is used to verify whether the user is registered or not.
Participating Actor	Mail user, Administrator, Employer or job seeker
Pre-condition	User must be registered.
Flow of event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user enters username and password.. 2. The system will check and give/hinder privilege to the user.
Exit Condition	Submitting the login form

Special Requirement	None
Use case Name	Browse Directory
Description	This use case will let the yellow page user to browse information.
Participating Actor	Yellow page user
Pre-condition	none
Flow of Event	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The system displays Yellow page homepage. 2. The user selects his/her choice from the page. 3. The system displays the detail information of the selected link.
Exit condition	The user Log out.
Special Requirement	None

3.4.3 Object Model

Class Diagram

3.4.4 Dynamic Model

3.4.4.1 Sequence Diagram

Fig 2 sequence diagram for create account

Fig 4 Sequence diagram for manage message

Fig 5 sequence diagram for compose message

Fig 7 Sequence diagram for Post vacancy

Fig 8 Sequence diagram for view vacancy

Fig 9 sequence diagram for browse directory

Fig 10 Sequence diagram for change language

Fig 11 Sequence diagram for login for addis mail

3.4.5. User Interface

ADDIS PORTAL HOMEPAGE (ENGLISH)

ADDIS PORTAL HOMEPAGE (AMHARIC)

ADDIS PORTAL HOMEPAGE (OROMIFA)

Addis! MAIL August 25, 2008

NEW MAIL USER

One AddisMail ID, so much Fun!

Send/Receive Mail in 4 different Languages!

[Sign Up](#)

Member Login

Username

Password

Copyright ©Addis Mail. All Rights Reserved.

ADDISMAIL HOMEPAGE

Addis! MAIL >> Inbox

Welcome **Yonas Amsalu** (sancy@addismail.com) Location: Ethiopia

August 25, 2008 [COMPOSE](#) [Edit Profile](#) [Logout](#)

Hotels Directory

- ◆ Sheraton Addis
- ◆ Addis Ababa Hilton
- ◆ Ghion Hotel
- ◆ Wabe Shebele Hotel
- ◆ Ras Hotel
- ◆ Ghion Hotel
- ◆ Wabe Shebele Hotel
- ◆ Ras Hotel

Historical Places

1. Baby Mama
2. Super Man
3. Made of Honor
4. Russell Peters Intense Comedy
5. Hitch
6. Analyze this
7. The Recruit
8. Meet the parent
9. Mr & Mrs Smith
10. Fink Panter

Colleges & Universities

1. Addis Ababa University
2. AAU Commerical College
3. Kotebe Teachers College
4. HiLCoE School of Computer Science & Technology
5. Micro Link College

Your Inbox

From	Title
challa	hello
Kebede	how are you

ADDISMAIL MAIN PAGE

ADDIS JOBS HOMEPAGE (ENGLISH)

ADDIS JOBS HOMEPAGE (AMHARIC)

ADDIS JOBS HOMEPAGE (TIGRIGNA)

ADDIS JOBS HOMEPAGE (OROMIFA)

ADDIS YELLOWPAGE HOMEPAGE (ENGLISH)

ADDIS YELLOWPAGE HOMEPAGE (AMHARIC)

ADDIS YELLOW PAGE - Homepage - Windows Internet Explorer

http://127.0.0.1/new%20portal/Oromifa/YELLOWPAGE/Index.php

ADDIS YELLOW PAGE - Homepage

Addis! YELLOW PAGES

Odeeffannoo waaee maali argachuu baybaaddu

Search

Location: Addis Ababa (Ethiopia)

August 25, 2008

Hotels Directory

- Sheraton Addis
- Addis Ababa Hilton
- Ghion Hotel
- Wabe Shebele Hotel
- Ras Hotel
- Ghion Hotel
- Wabe Shebele Hotel
- Ras Hotel

Historical Places

- Baby Mama
- Super Man
- Made of Honor
- Russell Peters Intense Comedy
- Hitch
- Analyze this
- The Recruit
- Meet the parent
- Mr & Mrs Smith
- Pink Panther

Colleges & Universities

- Addis Ababa University

Top Search Catalogue

HOSPITALS

Away from the noise of traffic and clamor of the city of Addis, perched on a hill with a gorgeous view, and a few minutes drive from city center, Located on Dessie road.

MUSEUMS

One of the best easily accessible hotel. Because it location is near to the Airport, it is well suited for business oriented customers. Moreover, it is well known for its bar service all over the Addis.

HOTELS

(1 item remaining) Waiting for http://127.0.0.1/new%20portal/Oromifa/YELLOWPAGE/Index.php...

Internet | Protected Mode: On

100%

ADDIS YELLOWPAGE HOMEPAGE (OROMIFA)

Part 3

System Design Document (SDD)

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of the system

In today's competitive world ICT become the order of the day and plays a dominant role in our daily activity and the progress of knowledge will not reach to the user without the flow of information from one end to the other. Therefore, the question now is how we can benefit From ICT to faster the overall development.

The purpose of our system is to provide a portal website service in four different languages. The system will be developed, especially for those who speak local languages. The services that we integrate in our system are:

- **Mailing Service:** a web based system where the user can send and read mails using four languages
- **Jobs searching Service:** a web based system that can be accessed by the both job seeker and employer using four languages
- **Yellow page Service:** a web based system that displays different information about Addis Ababa.

As it's mentioned in the previous document (RAD), the portal system has different purposes. Among the purposes, the main once are:

- Facilitate on line transmission of information
- Faster decision making
- Reduce error
- Supplies timely information for users.

1.2 Design goal

We can select design goals from the long list of highly desirable criteria. Under this section the qualities that the portal system should fulfill is listed. Based on this, while designing the system the following lists of design goals are considered.

A. Performance Criteria

This design goal Criteria includes the speed and space requirements imposed on the system. Should the system be responsive or should it accomplish a maximum number of tasks? Should memory be used effectively?

- **Response Time**

The system responds the user request within maximum of 5 seconds (This mainly depends on the Internet connection speed provided by ETC). Considering these we have selected an algorithm that we believe it's more efficient in terms of time. Using images and pictures to make the website usable may affect the response/download time of each page. However, to minimize this downloading time, we will optimize the image and picture file (GIF, JPEG)

B. Dependability Criteria

This design goal criteria determines how much effort should be expended in minimizing system crashes and their consequences. How available to the user should the system be? Are there security risks associated with the system environment? According to our system these will be describes as follows:

- **Accessibility**

Since the system is web based it is accessible through out the globe unless there is external constraint like power supply, economy...

- **Robustness**

The portal system will face different interactions from different users. Therefore; each interaction may bring an invalid input to the system. These invalid inputs may crash the system. The portal system will be implemented to capture any invalid data with Error Handling Mechanism. Therefore; any invalid data will be thrown and notified to the user as soon as possible.

- **Availability**

The portal system is allowed for any valid user of the system 24X7. Therefore; any user can access the services.

- **Security**

The portal system will be built with security methods. The user has to enter a user name and password so as to get in to one of the service. Therefore the system assures that any invalid user is not allowed to access it. Also the system is going to have a session which requires a user to log in again after predefined period of time.

- **Fault Tolerance**

The system has good ability to operate under erroneous condition and display the proper error message to correct the errors.

C. Maintenance Criteria

This design goal criteria determines how difficult it is to change the system after deployment. How easily can new functionality be added? How easily can existing functions are revised? Can the system be adapted to different application domain? According to the Portal system these design goal criteria will be described as follows:

- **Extensibility**

As we are using object Oriented Design, it is possible to add new functionality or new classes at any stage of development. Besides according to users need, it could be improper to add some functionality to the system. So the system's database and current methods should be carefully documented to add functionalities easily which makes the system flexible. Since the system is gong to use packages to gather all the functions of the system, the functionalities of the system will be

available for use by other systems and this also makes adding new functionalities easy.

- **Modifiability**

The portal system will be implemented to be modified easily by the developers. This is because comments and any documentation are available for the system functional part as well for non functional parts.

- **Adaptability**

The portal system can be deployed on a server supporting windows operating system. Therefore; any servers which support window operating system and which fulfill the requirements can adapt the system

- **Readability**

The portal system will be implemented using object oriented based with different classes. Each class has its own methods, events and properties. These class methods, events and properties will be written modularized or local function based. With this hierarchical classification; the system will have comments for each and every functions and importing different methods. Therefore; using the documentation and comments, any developer can understand the code behind the system as long as the developer knows the code editor.

1.3 Definitions and Abbreviations

Architecture: the organizational structure and associated behavior of the system.

DB: Database

IT: Information Technology

RAD: Requirement Analysis Document

UML: Unified Modeling Language

ETC: Ethiopian Telecommunications Corporation

1.4 References

- Bruegge B. and Dutoit A. Object-Oriented Software Engineering, Conquering Complex and Changing System, Pearson Education, 2002.
- senior projects papers ,[Mail and Chat provider,2005] ,[localization on open office,2006]
- Review of existing system e.g. yahoo.com,hotmail.com

2. Current Software Architecture

Currently system that can be considered as portal system is not available in local languages. It is common that any one who is looking forward to get the stated services has to use the services from world wide service providers like yahoo.com and other related sites. Even if it is not provided using local language we do have one web system that could provide recruitment service but regarding the yellow page system so far it's been done using manually.

The architecture used for the current system (Mail and job search) is a client/server architecture where a client can use Internet browsers to access the service provided by the system.

3. Proposed Software Architecture

3.1 Overview

The nature of this particular system requires that client-server architecture is the best. This mainly arises from the fact that the system runs over the World Wide Web (WWW), which has client/server architecture. This means that a client program running on a computer containing web browser requests information from a server program running on another computer somewhere on the Internet. That server then sends the requested data back over the Net to the browser program, which interprets and displays the data on our computer screen.

We will utilize the ISP Web Server. Note that the existing operating system of the Server that hosts the official website might be a UNIX or Window. At the client side, a variety of operating systems are assumed for the users of the system may have different types of operating systems.

Fig1. Proposed Architecture and how it works

The following steps explain the process graphically depicted in the above figure:

- 1) The client runs a Web browser (Internet explorer, for example) client program on the client computer.
- 2) The client connects to the Internet via a modem connection to an Internet Service Provider (ISP).
- 3) The client requests a page from a site on the Web. The client browser sends a message over the Internet that contains:
 - a. The transfer protocol (`http ://`)
 - b. The address, or Uniform Resource Locator (URL), e.g. `www.addisportal.com`
- 4) The server receives client's requests and sends the requested Web page, which is composed in HTML (Hypertext Markup Language).

- 5) The Server then transmits the requested page back across the Internet to the client computer.
- 6) The client browser program receives the HTML text and displays its interpretation of the page requested.

3.2 Sub system decomposition

The sub system is divided in to several major sub systems. The Sub systems available on the system are:

- **Addis Mail Sub System**

The Addis Mail subsystem is responsible for the services that are to be provided by the mail server part which is responsible for the sending and receiving of text messages using four languages.

- **Addis Job Sub System**

The Addis Jobs subsystem is responsible for the services that are to be provided by the Addis Jobs server part which is responsible for the registering both employer and job seeker for making the recruitment process easier. This system also implemented using four languages.

- **Addis Yellow page Sub System**

The Addis Yellow page Provider subsystem is responsible for the services that are to be provided by the Addis Yellow page server part which is responsible for posting different information about Ethiopia. This system also implemented using four languages.

3.3 Hardware software mapping

In the Addis Portal System, all the subsystems will permanently reside on the ISP server i.e. the ISP Web Server that will host the pages. Whenever a client browses the site and some part of the subsystems will be transported to the client machine.

The following are the machines that will be involved in System operation:

1. **ISP Web Server:** It is the server where the Addis Portal official Web site resides. Since each system is part of the Addis Portal official Web site it will also reside on the ISP Web Server for a better performance.
2. **Client Machine:** The client machine is the machine from which the user will access the Addis Portal system. This client machine can be anywhere in the world.

Fig 2: Deployment Diagram

3.4 Persistent Data Management

The Portal system stores its data in the database. Users access these files from different location according to their permission on the data. After finishing the system will put the data with its modified content and stores permanently for further use.

Portal system Database: is well organized data storage mechanizes in the operating system. This data could be flat files (simple memos), relational or some other types. The Portal system uses a relational database, to store data that comes from the clients. It will be implemented using Microsoft SQL server 2000®. Implementing using this has advantage of supporting multi-user and can store a lot of data. In relational Database, data are stored in tables that comply with predefined type called schema. Each column in a table represents an attribute. Each row represents a data item of the attribute values. Several records in different tables represent the attributes of an individual object. Then, the object will be accessed from different development frameworks.

ER-Diagram for Mail

ER-Diagram for Job Search Service

3.5 Access Control Executing

The portal system needs persistent storage for storing information related to the following entities:

- Addis Mail user entities
- Addis Jobs user entities
- Addis Yellow page user entities

The Portal system will be developed to support users from different location with their permission.

Security is one of the primary concerns of any institution or indeed any individual using computers. Security must therefore consider external environment of the system, and protect it from:

- Unauthorized access
- Malicious modification or destruction
- Accidental introduction of inconsistency

User authentication methods are used in protecting special sections of the site documents meant to be accessed only by individuals with the proper clearance as determined by an appropriate set of identification credentials. The security provisions can be achieved by requiring that:

- User Identity is established through passwords (encrypted)
- Passwords must be kept secret
- Frequent change of passwords by the holder
- Use of a “non-guessable” passwords (not in dictionary or username)
- All invalid login attempts are logged in a special file for reference.

Therefore, all access-control decisions break down to who is allowed to do what. In this model, a principal represents the “who”, “a target represents the “what”, and the privileges associated with a principal represent the authorization (or denial of authorization) for a principal to access a specific target.

Access Matrix

Actor	Attributes	Operation
Mail user	Mail_id M_from M_date M_subject	Create_mail_id() Get_M_from() Get_M_date() Get_Mail_subject()
Job Search User	Account_id J_viewvacancy J_buildcv J_Postvacancy	Create_Jobsearch_id() Get_J_view() Get_J_buildcv() Get_Job_postvacancy

User's info	User_id Firstname Lastname Username Userpassword Sec_question Answer	Create_User_id () Get_Firstname Get_Lastname Get_Username Get_Userpassword Get_Sec_question Get_Answer

Authentication and Authorization Mechanism

The verification or validation users on the system will be described in a sequence of steps.

1. The system accepts user login information from user.
2. The system will validate the user login information from two different places. The first is whether a user has an account on the Portal system. i.e. Its authentication and second even if the user has an account it check its permission i.e. its authorization.
3. Then the system will send an acknowledgment for the user for any status.
4. If the acknowledgement of the system is "Error Login", the user is allowed to prompt his/her login information again for three times.

3.6 Global Software Control

The Control flow mechanism of our system is a combination of event Driven and Threads since the system runs over the Internet, which requires both of the mechanisms. The server waits for requires from the web browser. Up on the receipt of a request (message), the server processes it and dispatches it to the appropriate task, thus resulting in an event based control flow.

3.7 Boundary Condition

The boundary condition describes the installation, start up, shut down and error behavior of the system. The condition must be examined in two different locations, Client side and server side.

- **Installation**

The Portal system must be installed in window based operating system only.

- **Start up**

As soon as the Portal system deployment setup finished the system will initialized When we come to the system the starting condition of the system is when the administrator starts on the server and the start up is finished, the user in the client machine establish the condition. The server populates the client machine with what the client machine has asked for.

- **Shut down**

The server must not be closed. This is because the time the client access the system data is not determined. When the client accesses the necessary data's and wants close the system. Clicking the "right most button" or "X" button on the screen closes the Portal system from the client side.

- **Error Behaviors**

On the server side the server and the system must be protected from unauthorized person and viruses. Unless files modified or deleted, it cannot behave an error. On the client side system is developed using built-in and custom error handler mechanisms. If error happens the user will be notified immediately.

4. Subsystem Services

1. The mail service Sub system

Class Mail

This is the part that is responsible for sending and receiving mail

2. The Job Search System

Class Job Search

This is the part that is responsible for posting and viewing vacancies

3. The Yellow page system

Class Yellow page

This is the part that is responsible fro viewing information

Attribute	Data type	Description	Operation	Operation Description
Mail_id M_from M_date M-subject M_message	Char nvarchar nvarchar smalldatetime ntext(255)	Mail ID Mail From Mail Date Mail subject Mail Message	Create_mail_id () Get_M_from () Get_M_date () Get_Mail_subject ()	+ Generate mail id +Get Mail + Get date +Get Mail Subject
User_id First name Last name Username User password Sec_question Answer	Int nvarchar nvarchar nvarchar nvarchar nvarchar nvarchar	User Id User First name User Last name User's Username User's password User's Secret Question User's Answer	Create_User_Id () Get_First name () Get_Last name () Get_Username () Get_Userpassword () Get_Sec_question () Get_Answer ()	+Generate User id +Get Personal information +Get Secret Question +Get answer

Part 4

Object Design Document

(ODD)

1. Introduction

Addis portal is a localized web based system aimed to provide a quality mailing, job searching and yellow page service.

Its mission is to provide free and useful system to help people solve the problems of every day life using Amharic, oromifa and Tigregna language. The system is not only aimed in providing free and precise service but will also provide an up to date information, a job search service which lets the users to post vacancy.

1.1 Object design trade-off

Memory vs. Response time

Fast response time is always the preferred factor by the users in doing a certain task. Since, fast response time involve a huge amount of memory depending on the number of users currently logged into the system. The system might be used by various users at the same time, thus users may not get the service that they want faster. In order to overcome the response time problem the system needs to have a huge amount of memory.

Speed Vs. user interface Design

The user interface is a part of the system that user will always interact with. In order to minimize the load time of interfaces, the system interfaces were designed with limited amount of picture and graphical material.

1.2 Interface Documentation Guidelines

Interface documentation guideline is one of the most important factors that can improve communication between developers during object design. This

includes a list of rules that can improve communication between developers during object design. Some of the rules used in the design on the system are:

- Use of comments in the code in order to facilitate understanding and readability of the code for developers or system administrators in time of maintenance and upgrade.
- Function and Class Names should be descriptive of their functions.
- Variable should be explicitly declared.
- Classes are names with singular nouns.

1.3 Definition, acronyms, and abbreviations

ODD: - This Document, it is an abbreviation for Object Design Document

RAD: - An acronym for Requirement Analysis Document

SDD: - An acronym for System Design Document

1.4 References

Addis Portal System, Requirement Analysis Document (RAD).

Addis Portal System, System Design Document (SDD).

3. Class Interface

Class interface of a system is composed of different classes that have been defined in the Requirement Analysis and System Design Document phases. A class interface is a description of a class, its dependencies with other classes and packages, its attributes and operations. The class interface of the system is defined as follows.

Part 5

Implementation (Coding)

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head>
<LINK href="_style.css" title="text/css" rel="stylesheet" />
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1" />
<title>&#4768;&#4850;&#4661;PORTAL - Homepage</title>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style135 {color: #003366; font-size: 9px; font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; }
.style15 {
    font-family: Tahoma;
    font-size: 10px;
    color: #000000;
}
.style17 {color: #FF0000}
.style20 {font-size: 10px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; }
.style21 {font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif}
.style124 {font-size: 24px; font-weight: bold; color: #006633; }
.style123 {font-size: 12px}
.style136 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; }
.style16 {    font-size: 10px;
    font-weight: bold;
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif, "Aliens ate my mum", "ESRI
Hydrants", "ESRI Hazardous Materials", "ESRI Geometric Symbols", "ESRI Geology USGS 95-
525", "ESRI Geology AGSO 1", "ESRI Geology", "ESRI Fire Incident NFPA", "ESRI Environmental
& Icons", "ESRI Enviro Hazard Sites", "Eras Bold ITC", "Engravers MT", Elephant, "Edwardian
Script ITC", DS-Digital, "Curlz MT", "Courier New", Courier, "Copperplate Gothic Light",
"Copperplate Gothic Bold", "Cooper Black", Chiller, "Chinese Takeaway", "Colonna MT";
    color: #FF0000;
}
.style138 {
    color: #FFFFFF;
    font-size: 12px;
}
.style143 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #006699; }
.style145 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Tahoma; }
.style146 {
    color: #9ECF40;
    font-family: Geneva, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-size: 12px;
}
.style111 {
    font-size: 12px;
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    color: #006699;
}
.style148 {
    font-size: 9pt;
    font-family: Tahoma;
}
.style153 {font-size: 10px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #006699; }
.style167 {color: #003366; font-size: 9; }
.style168 {font-size: 9; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #003366; }
.style169 {

```

```

        font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
        font-size: 9px;
    }
    .style171 {font-size: 7px}
    .style172 {font-size: 9px}
    .style174 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Tahoma; color: #006699;}
    .style178 {color: #FFFFFF}
    .style179 {font-size: 10px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #FFFFFF;}
    .style183 {    font-size: 18px;
        color: #003366;
    }
}
-->
</style>
<SCRIPT LANGUAGE="JavaScript">
<!-- Original: Jeff Harding (jbh@site-ations.com) -->
<!-- Web Site: http://www.site-ations.com -->

<!-- Day images (c): http://www.site-ations.com -->
<!-- Month images (c): http://www.bruce-hamilton.com -->

```

```

<!-- Begin
theDate= new Date();
months = new Array();
days = new Array();
months[1] ="Images/date-images/jan.gif";
months[2] ="Images/date-images/feb.gif";
months[3] ="Images/date-images/mar.gif";
months[4] ="Images/date-images/apr.gif";
months[5] ="Images/date-images/may.gif";
months[6] ="Images/date-images/jun.gif";
months[7] ="Images/date-images/jul.gif";
months[8] ="Images/date-images/aug.gif";
months[9] ="Images/date-images/sep.gif";
months[10] ="Images/date-images/oct.gif";
months[11] ="Images/date-images/nov.gif";
months[12] ="Images/date-images/dec.gif";
days[1] ="Images/date-images/1st.gif";
days[2] ="Images/date-images/2nd.gif";
days[3] ="Images/date-images/3rd.gif";
days[4] ="Images/date-images/4th.gif";
days[5] ="Images/date-images/5th.gif";
days[6] ="Images/date-images/6th.gif";
days[7] ="Images/date-images/7th.gif";
days[8] ="Images/date-images/8th.gif";
days[9] ="Images/date-images/9th.gif";
days[10] ="Images/date-images/10th.gif";
days[11] ="Images/date-images/11th.gif";
days[12] ="Images/date-images/12th.gif";
days[13] ="Images/date-images/13th.gif";
days[14] ="Images/date-images/14th.gif";
days[15] ="Images/date-images/15th.gif";
days[16] ="Images/date-images/16th.gif";

```



```

        </tr>
    </table></th>
</tr>
</table></td>
    </tr>
<tr>
    <th width="23%" height="1090" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
        <tr valign="top">
            <th height="83" scope="row"><table width="96%" border="1" align="left"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                <tr>
                    <td height="72"><div align="center"></div></td>
                </tr>
            </table></th>
        </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
            <th height="1007" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                <tr valign="top">
                    <th height="1007" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                        <tr valign="top">
                            <td width="79%" height="1007"><table width="100%" border="0" align="left"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                                <tr valign="top">
                                    <th height="1003" scope="row"><table width="96%" border="1"
bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="border-collapse:collapse" >
                                        <tr><td class="style16"><div
align="center">Welcome to addisportal</div></td>
                                        </tr>
                                    </tr>
                                </table></th>
                                <td height="915"></td>
                                </tr>
                            </table></th>
                        </tr>
                    </table></td>
                </tr>
            </table></th>
        </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></td>
    </tr>
</table></td>
    <td width="77%" class="style135"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr valign="top">
            <th height="1064" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                <tr valign="top">
                    <th height="160" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">

```

```

        <tr>
            <th width="44%" height="151"
scope="row"><script>printDate();</script></th>
            <td width="56%"><div align="center">
                <object classid="clsid:D27CDB6E-AE6D-11cf-96B8-444553540000"
codebase="http://download.macromedia.com/pub/shockwave/cabs/flash/swflash.cab#versio
n=7,0,19,0" width="391" height="149" title="animation">
                    <param name="movie" value="Images/animation1.swf" />
                    <param name="quality" value="high" />
                    <embed src="Images/animation1.swf" quality="high"
pluginspage="http://www.macromedia.com/go/getflashplayer" type="application/x-
shockwave-flash" width="391" height="149"></embed>
                </object>
            </div></td>
        </tr>
    </table></th>
</tr>
<tr>
    <th height="39" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellpadding="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <th width="35%" height="35" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
                <tr>
                    <th width="9%" scope="row"><div align="right"></div></th>
                    <td width="86%" bgcolor="#2E99CD"><div align="center"><span
class="style138"><a href="MAIL/Index.php"
class="menu">ADDISMAIL</a></span></div></td>
                    <td width="5%"><div align="left"></div></td>
                </tr>
            </table></th>
            <td width="33%"><table width="98%" border="0" cellpadding="0">
                <tr>
                    <th width="9%" scope="row"><div align="right"></div></th>
                    <td width="86%" bgcolor="#2E99CD"><div align="center"><span
class="menu style148"><a href="JOBS/Index.php"
class="menu">ADDISJOBS</a></span></div></td>
                    <td width="5%"><div align="left"></div></td>
                </tr>
            </table></td>
            <td width="32%"><table width="100%" border="0" cellpadding="0"
cellpadding="0">
                <tr>
                    <th width="9%" scope="row"><div align="right"></div></th>
                    <td width="86%" bgcolor="#2E99CD"><div align="center"><a
href="YELLOWPAGE/Index.htm" class="menu">ADDISYELLOWPAGE</a></div></td>
                    <td width="5%"><div align="left"></div></td>
                </tr>
            </table>

```

```

        </table></td>
    </tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
<tr>
    <th height="117" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <th height="59" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                <tr>
                    <td width="66%" height="59"><table width="98%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
                        <tr>
                            <th width="2%" rowspan="2" scope="row">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</th>
                            <td width="98%"><div align="left"><span class="style124"><span
class="style17">&#4632;&#4621;&#4779;&#4637;</span> &#4768;&#4850;&#4661;
&#4819;&#4632;&#4725;
&#4845;&#4609;&#4757;&#4621;&#4814;!</span></div></td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <td height="10"><hr color="#d2e4fc" /></td>
                            </tr>
                        </table></td>
                    <td width="34%"><table width="86%" border="0" align="right"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
                        <tr>
                            <td width="41%"><label>
                                <input name="textfield" type="text" class="style135" size="24" />
                            </label></td>
                            <td width="46%"><input name="submit" type="submit"
style="BORDER-RIGHT: medium none; BORDER-TOP: medium none; BACKGROUND: #99cccc;
FONT: 8pt tahoma; BORDER-LEFT: medium none; BORDER-BOTTOM: medium none"
value="SEARCH" /></td>
                        </tr>
                    </table></td>
                </tr>
            </table></th>
        </table></th>
    </tr>
<tr>
    <th height="49" scope="row"><div align="justify"><span class="style15">
<span class="style21">Addis Portal is designed by integrating different services into one. The
services that are available in this website are Mailing, Job Search and Yellowpage. You can get
those services in four different languages. </span></span></div></th>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
<tr>
    <th height="487" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr valign="top">
            <th width="48%" height="638" scope="row"><table width="98%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
                <tr valign="top">

```

```

        <th height="110" scope="row"><table width="98%" border="1" align="left"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr>
            <td height="16" bgcolor="#D6E6E9"><div align="left"
class="style145">  Addis
Ababa </div></td>
            </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
            <td height="133"><table width="100%" border="0" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
                <tr>
                    <th width="49%" height="128" scope="row"></th>
                    <td width="51%"><div align="justify">
                        <table width="90%" border="0" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
                            <tr>
                                <th scope="row"><div align="justify" class="style21"><font
color="#006699"> Addis
                                    Ababa, capital and largest city of Ethiopia,
                                    the country's commercial, manufacturing,
                                    and cultural center </font><font color="#006699" size="2"
face="Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif"><br />
                                    <span class="style153">Addis Ababa is a sprawling city,
well
                                        wooded, especially with eucalyptus trees,
                                        and crossed by broad avenues.</span></font></div></th>
                                </tr>
                            </table>
                        </div></td>
                    </tr>
                </table></td>
            </tr>
        </table></th>
        <tr>
            <th height="12" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
        </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
            <th height="306" scope="row"><table width="98%" border="1" align="left"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                <tr>
                    <td bgcolor="#D6E6E9"
class="style145"><div align="left"> Entertainment</div></td>
                </tr>
            </table>
        </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
            <td height="453"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                <tr>
                    <th width="48%" height="451" scope="row"><table width="95%"
border="1" align="center" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc"
style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                        <tr>

```

```
 &nbsp; Music</div></td> </tr> <tr> <th height="425" scope="row">&nbsp;</th> </tr> </table></th> <td width="52%"><table width="95%" border="1" align="center" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse"> <tr> <td align="left"> &nbsp; Movies</div></td> </tr> <tr valign="top"> <th height="423" scope="row"><table width="99%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0"> <tr> <th height="38" bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style153" scope="row"> Russel Peters Standup commedy </th> </tr> <tr> <th height="122" scope="row"><embed src="media/A1Russell Peters.wmv" width="118" height="114" autostart="false"></embed></th> </tr> <tr> <th bgcolor="#993300" class="style179" scope="row">download</a></th> </tr> <tr> <th scope="row"><hr /></th> </tr> <tr> <th height="38" bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style153" scope="row"> 24 (Season 7) Trailer </th> </tr> <tr> <th height="122" scope="row"><embed src="media/SeasonTrailer (1).mpg" width="118" height="114" autostart="False"></embed></th> </tr> <tr> <th bgcolor="#993300" class="style153 style178" scope="row">download</th> </tr> <tr> <th height="57" scope="row">&nbsp;</th> </tr> </table></td> </tr> </table></td> </tr> |
```

```

        </table></td>
    </tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></th>
    <td width="52%"><table width="98%" border="0" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
    <tr valign="top">
        <th height="453" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
            <tr valign="top">
                <td height="213"><table width="100%" height="64%" border="0"
align="center" bordercolor="#a0ce41" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                    <tr>
                        <td height="18" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style16"><table
width="100%" border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
                            <tr>
                                <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF"><div align="right"></div></td>
                                <td width="96%" background="Images/bg.gif"><div
align="left">
                                    <table width="99%" border="0" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
                                        <tr>
                                            <th scope="row"><div align="left"><span
class="style174">
ADVERTISMENT</span></div></th>
                                            <td><div align="right"></div></td>
                                        </tr>
                                    </table>
                                </div></td>
                                <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><div
align="left"></div></td>
                            </tr>
                        </table></td>
                    </tr>
                </table></th>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
    </tr>
<tr>
    <td bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style136">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
    <td height="220" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><table
width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#9ECF40"
style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr>
            <th width="36%" height="62" scope="row"><table
width="100%" border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
                <tr>
                    <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
                    <td width="40%" class="style20"><div align="justify"><a
href="Advertisement.htm" class="menu1">Sanoy Computer Center 30% OFF </a></div></td>
                </tr>
            </table></th>
        </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>

```

```

        <td width="31%"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
            <td width="40%" class="style20"><div align="justify"><a
href="Advertismment.htm" class="menu1">Sanoy Computer Center 30% OFF </a></div></td>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        <td width="33%"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
            <td width="40%" class="style20"><div align="justify"><a
href="Advertismment.htm" class="menu1">Sanoy Computer Center 30% OFF </a></div></td>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
</tr>
<tr>
<th height="64" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
            <td width="40%" class="style20"><div align="justify"><a
href="Advertismment.htm" class="menu1">Sanoy Computer Center 30% OFF </a></div></td>
        </tr>
        </table></th>
        <td><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
            <td width="40%" class="style20"><div align="justify"><a
href="Advertismment.htm" class="menu1">Sanoy Computer Center 30% OFF </a></div></td>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        <td><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
            <td width="40%" class="style20"><div align="justify"><a
href="Advertismment.htm" class="menu1">Sanoy Computer Center 30% OFF </a></div></td>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        <td><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>

```



```

        <tr valign="top">
            <td height="121" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><table
width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#9ECF40"
style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                <tr valign="top">
                    <td height="92"><table width="100%" height="75%"
border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
                        <tr>
                            <td width="40%" height="90"><div align="center"><a
href="MAIL/Registration.htm"></a></div></td>
                            <td width="4%">&nbsp;</td>
                            <td width="56%"></td>
                        </tr>
                    </table></td>
                </tr>
            </table></td>
        </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td><table width="100%" height="64%" border="0" align="center"
bordercolor="#a0ce41" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr>
            <td height="18" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style16"><table
width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
                <tr>
                    <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF"><div align="right"></div></td>
                    <td width="96%" background="Images/bg.gif"><div
align="left">
                        <table width="99%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                            <tr>
                                <th scope="row"><div align="left"><span
class="style174">
ADVERTISEMENT</span></div></th>
                                <td><div align="right"></div></td>
                            </tr>
                        </table>
                    </div></td>
                    <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><div
align="left"></div></td>
                </tr>
            </table></td>
        </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style136">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">

```

```

        <td height="77" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><table
width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#9ECF40"
style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr valign="top">
        <td height="92"><table width="100%" height="75%"
border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
        <tr>
        <td width="40%" height="90"><div align="center"></div></td>
        <td width="4%">&nbsp;</td>
        <td width="56%"></td>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        </tr>
        </table></th>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        </tr>
        </table></th>
        </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
        <th height="129" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr>
        <td height="127"><object classid="clsid:D27CDB6E-AE6D-11cf-96B8-
444553540000"
codebase="http://download.macromedia.com/pub/shockwave/cabs/flash/swflash.cab#versio
n=7,0,19,0" width="656" height="120" title="animation">
        <param name="movie" value="Images/animation1.swf" />
        <param name="quality" value="high" />
        <embed src="Images/animation1.swf" quality="high"
pluginspage="http://www.macromedia.com/go/getflashplayer" type="application/x-
shockwave-flash" width="656" height="120"></embed>
        </object></td>
        </tr>
        </table></th>
        </tr>
        </table></th>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        </tr>
        </table></th>
        </tr>
        </table></td>
        </tr>
        <tr valign="top"><td height="21"><table width="98%" border="1" align="center"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" bgcolor="#F5F6FA" style="BORDER-
COLLAPSE: collapse">

```

```

    <th height="19" scope="row"><span class="style153"> Copyright &copy;Addis Portal . All
Rights Reserved.</span></th>
  </tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-

```

```

transitional.dtd">
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head>
<LINK href="../_style2.css" title="text/css" rel="stylesheet" />
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1" />
<title>&#4768;&#4850;&#4661;!JOBS - Homepage</title>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style6 {font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif}
.style7 {
    font-size: 18px;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-weight: bold;
}
.style153 {
    font-size: 10px;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    color: #000000;
    font-weight: bold;
}
.style19 {
    font-size: 10px;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
}
.style143 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #006699;}
.style146 {    color: #9ECF40;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-size: 12px;
}
.style35 {font-size: 12px}
.style38 {
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-size: 18px;
    color: #003366;
}
.style43 {
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-size: 12px;
    font-weight: bold;
}
.style45 {color: #003366}
-->
</style>

```

```

</head>

<body bgColor=#eaeaf4>
<p>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</p>
<table width="75%" border="1" align="center" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0"
bordercolor="#333333" style="border-

collapse:collapse">
  <tr valign="top">
    <td height="437"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
      <tr valign="top">
        <td height="83"><table width="100%" border="1" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0"
style="border-

collapse:collapse">
          <tr>
            <td bgcolor="#D6E6E9" class="style7 style45">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Addis! MAIL </td>
          </tr>
          <tr>
            <td height="61" bgcolor="#EEEEEE"><div align="RIGHT"><font size="2" face="Verdana,
Arial, Helvetica,

sans-serif">
              <SCRIPT language=JAVASCRIPT>
                <!--
                var m_names = new Array("January", "February", "March",
                "April", "May", "June", "July", "August", "September",
                "October", "November", "December");

                var d = new Date();
                var curr_date = d.getDate();
                var sup = "";
                var curr_month = d.getMonth();
                var curr_year = d.getFullYear();

                document.write(m_names[curr_month] + "<SUP>" + sup + "</SUP> "
                + curr_date + ", " + curr_year);

                //-->
              </SCRIPT>
            </font>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</div></td>
          </tr>
        </table></td>
      </tr>
    </table></td>
  </tr>
  <tr bgcolor="#e8f0f8">
    <td>&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</td>
  </tr>
  <tr valign="top" bgcolor="#e8f0f8">
    <td height="330"><table width="98%" border="0" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0"

bgcolor="#FFFFFF">
      <tr valign="top">

```

```

        <td width="33%" height="333"><table width="91%" border="0" align="center"
cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
    <tr>
        <td height="19"></td>
    </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
            <td><table width="97%" height="100%" border="1" align="right" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0"
bordercolor="#afc3ea" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                <tr>
                    <th height="257" class="style146" scope="row"></th>
                </tr>
            </table></td>
        </tr>
    </table></td>
    <td width="67%"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <td>&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
            <td height="266"><table width="98%" border="0" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0"
bordercolor="#afc3ea" style="
                BORDER-COLLAPSE:collapse">
                    <tr valign="top">
                        <td width="60%" height="263"><table width="98%" border="1" align="center"
cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#afc3ea" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                            <tr valign="top">
                                <td height="213"><table cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" width="100%"
                                    bgcolor="#FFFFFF" border="0">
                                        <tbody>
                                            <tr>
                                                <td height="25" valign="top" class="text-small-black"><table cellpadding="0"
cellpadding="0" width="100%"
                                    bgcolor="#efefef" border="0">
                                        <!--DWLayoutTable-->
                                        <tbody>
                                            <tr valign="center">
                                                <td
width="100%" height="18" valign="top" class="text-middle-blue
style45">&nbsp; &nbsp;<span class="style43">NEW MAIL USER
</span></td>
        <td valign="center" align="right" width="83"><!--DWLayoutEmptyCell--
>&nbsp;</td>
        </tr>
    </tbody>
</table></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td height="149" valign="top" class="text-small-black"><p align="center"
class="style43">&nbsp;</p>
        <table width="81%" border="0" align="center">
            <tr>
                <td height="88"><p align="center" class="style143">One AddisMail ID,
so much
Fun! </p>
                <p align="center" class="style143">Send/Receive Mail in 4 different
Languages!</p></td>
            </tr>
        </table>
    </tr>
<tr>
    <td align="center" valign="bottom" align="middle" height="50"><div
align="center"></div></td>
    </tr>
</tbody>
</table></td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
    <td height="31"><div align="center"><a href="Registration.php"
class="name">Sign Up
</a></div></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
<td width="40%"><table width="97%" height="100%" border="1" align="right"
cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#afc3ea" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
    <tr>
        <th height="35" bgcolor="#D6E6E9" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style6"><span
class="style35"> &nbsp; Member Login
</span></div></th>
    </tr>
</tr>

```

```

        <th height="218" class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style19"><form
action="VerifyMailUser.php" method="post"><table width="95%" border="0" align="center">
    <tr>
        <td><table width="90%" border="0" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
            <tr>
                <td height="63" colspan="2"><div align="center"></div></td>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <td width="33%"><span class="style19">Username</span></td>
                <td width="67%"><label>
                    <input name="txtUsername" type="text" id="txtUsername" size="15" />
                </label></td>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <td height="21"><span class="style19">Password</span></td>
                <td><input name="txtPassword" type="password" id="txtPassword" size="15"
/></td>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <td height="44" colspan="2"><label>
                    <div align="center">
                        <input type="submit" name="Submit22" value="Login" />
                    </div>
                </label></td>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
    </tr>
</table></form></div>
        </th>
    </table></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td colspan="2" bgcolor="#e8f0f8"><div align="center"><span
class="style153">Copyright &copy;Addis
Mail. All Rights Reserved.</span></div></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>

```

```

<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head>
<LINK href="../_style2.css" title="text/css" rel="stylesheet" />
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1" />
<title>&#4768;&#4850;&#4661;!YELLOW PAGE - Homepage</title>
<SCRIPT LANGUAGE="JavaScript">
function form_valid(txt){
var catagory;
catagory =(document.search1.cmbCatagory.value);
var returnValue = false;
if(catagory == "- Select -"){
window.alert("Please Select from the Catagory List!");
}
else{
returnValue = true;
}

return returnValue;

}

</SCRIPT>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style2 {
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-size: 14px;
}
.style4 {
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-size: 12px;
}
.style5 {
    font-size: 12px;
    font-weight: bold;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
}
.style6 {font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif}
.style7 {
    font-size: 18px;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-weight: bold;
}
.style153 {
    font-size: 10px;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    color: #000000;
    font-weight: bold;
}
.style19 {
    font-size: 10px;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
}

```

```

.style20 {
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif, "Aliens ate my mum", "ESRI
Hydrants", "ESRI Hazardous Materials", "ESRI Geometric Symbols", "ESRI Geology USGS 95-
525", "ESRI Geology AGSO 1", "ESRI Geology", "ESRI Fire Incident NFPA", "ESRI Environmental
& Icons", "ESRI Enviro Hazard Sites", "Eras Bold ITC", "Engravers MT", Elephant, "Edwardian
Script ITC", DS-Digital, "Curlz MT", "Courier New", Courier, "Copperplate Gothic Light",
"Copperplate Gothic Bold", "Cooper Black", Chiller, "Chinese Takeaway", "Colonna MT";
    font-size: 14px;
    color: #999900;
}
.style32 {font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif, "Aliens ate my mum", "ESRI
Hydrants", "ESRI Hazardous Materials", "ESRI Geometric Symbols", "ESRI Geology USGS 95-
525", "ESRI Geology AGSO 1", "ESRI Geology", "ESRI Fire Incident NFPA", "ESRI Environmental
& Icons", "ESRI Enviro Hazard Sites", "Eras Bold ITC", "Engravers MT", Elephant, "Edwardian
Script ITC", DS-Digital, "Curlz MT", "Courier New", Courier, "Copperplate Gothic Light",
"Copperplate Gothic Bold", "Cooper Black", Chiller, "Chinese Takeaway", "Colonna MT"; font-
size: 10px; }
.style143 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #006699; }
.style146 {    color: #9ECF40;
    font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-size: 12px;
}
.style168 {font-size: 9; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #003366; }
.style34 {font-size: 11px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; }
.style35 {font-size: 12px}
-->
</style>
</head>

<body bgColor=#eaeaf4><table width="75%" border="1" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d89a2d" style="border-collapse:collapse">
  <tr valign="top">
    <td height="706"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
      <tr valign="top">
        <td height="83"><table width="100%" border="1" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0"
style="border-collapse:collapse">
          <tr>
            <td bgcolor="#ffcc69" class="style7">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;Addis! YELLOW PAGES </td>
          </tr>
          <tr>
            <td height="61" bgcolor="#EEEEEE"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
              <tr valign="bottom">
                <td width="44%"><form name="search1" action="SearchResult.php" method="post"
onSubmit="return form_valid()"><table width="94%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                  <tr>
                    <td width="32%"><div align="right"><span class="style2">&nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;<span
class="style5">Your Search</span><span class="style6">: &nbsp;&nbsp;&nbsp;</span>
</span></div></td>
                    <td width="41%"><select name="cmbCatagory" id="cmbCatagory" >
                      <option selected="selected">- Select -</option>
                      <option>Hotel</option>
                      <option>Museum</option>
                      <option>Historical Places</option>

```



```

var curr_year = d.getFullYear();

document.write(m_names[curr_month] + "<SUP>" + sup + "</SUP> "
+ curr_date + ", " + curr_year);

//-->
        </SCRIPT>
        </font></p>
        <p>&nbsp;</p>
        </div></td>
    </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
            <td><table width="97%" height="100%" border="1" align="right" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#ffcc69" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                <tr>
                    <th height="35" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style6"><span
class="style35"> &nbsp; Hotels Directory </span></div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style19">&nbsp;&nbsp;<img alt="Sheraton Addis" /></div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style19">&nbsp;Addis Ababa Hilton </div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style19">&nbsp;Ghion Hotel </div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style19">&nbsp;Wabe Shebele Hotel </div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style19">&nbsp;Ras Hotel </div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style19">&nbsp;Ghion Hotel </div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style19">&nbsp;Wabe Shebele Hotel </div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style19">&nbsp;Ras Hotel </div></th>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <th height="42" class="style146" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
                </tr>
            </td>
        </tr>

```

```

        <th height="33" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style6"><span
class="style35"> &nbsp; Historical Places </span></div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168"> 1. Baby Mama
</div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">2. Super Man
</div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">3. Made of
Honor </div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">4. Russell
Peters Intense Comedy </div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">5. Hitch
</div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">6. Analyze this
</div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">7. The Recruit
</div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">8. Meet the
parent </div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">9. Mr &
Mrs Smith </div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">10. Pink Panther
</div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th height="33" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style6"><span
class="style35"> &nbsp;Colleges & Universities </span></div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168"> 1. Addis Ababa
University </div></th>
    </tr>
    <tr>

```

```

                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">2. AAU
Commerical College </div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">3. Kotebe
Teachers College </div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">4. HiLCoE
School of Computer Science & Technology </div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">5. Micro Link
College </div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">6. CPU College
</div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">7. Unity College
</div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">8. Admas
College </div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">9. Zega College
</div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th class="style19" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">10. Africa Beza
College </div></th>
            </tr>
            <tr>
                <th height="40" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
    </tr>

```

```

</table></td>
<td width="77%"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
<tr>
<td><table width="98%" border="0" align="center" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
<tr>
<td height="62"><object classid="clsid:D27CDB6E-AE6D-11cf-96B8-
444553540000"
codebase="http://download.macromedia.com/pub/shockwave/cabs/flash/swflash.cab#versio
n=7,0,19,0" width="100%" height="50" align="middle" title="animation">
<param name="movie" value="Images/animation1.swf" />
<param name="quality" value="high" />
<embed src="Images/animation1.swf" width="100%" height="50" align="middle"
quality="high" pluginspage="http://www.macromedia.com/go/getflashplayer"
type="application/x-shockwave-flash"></embed>

```

```

        </object></td>
    </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>

<tr valign="top">
    <td height="487"><table width="98%" border="1" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#ffcc69" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr valign="top">
            <td height="599"><table width="90%" border="0" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
                <tr>
                    <td height="78"><span class="style20">Top Search Catalogue</span></td>
                </tr>
                <tr>
                    <td height="514"><table width="98%" border="0" cellpadding="0"
cellpadding="0">
                        <tr>
                            <td width="27%" height="109"><table width="98%" border="1" align="center"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
                                <tr>
                                    <td height="111"><div align="center"></div></td>
                                </tr>
                            </table></td>
                            <td width="2%">&nbsp;</td>
                            <td width="71%"><p class="style32">HOSPITALS</p>
                            <p class="style32">Away from the noise of traffic and
                            clamor of the city of Addis, perched on a hill with a gorgeous
                            view, and a few minutes drive from city center, Located on
                            Dessie road.</p></td>
                        </tr>
                        <tr>
                            <td>&nbsp;</td>
                            <td>&nbsp;</td>
                            <td>&nbsp;</td>
                        </tr>
                        <tr>
                            <td height="109"><table width="98%" border="1" align="center"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
                                <tr>
                                    <td height="109"><div align="center"></div></td>
                                </tr>
                            </table></td>
                            <td>&nbsp;</td>
                            <td><p class="style32">MUSEUMS</p>
                            <p class="style32"> One of the best easily accessible
                            hotel. Because it location is near to the Airport, it is well
                            suited for business oriented customers. Moreover, it is well
                            known for its bar service all over the
                            Addis.</p></td>
                        </tr>
                        <tr>
                            <td>&nbsp;</td>
                    </tr>
                <td>&nbsp;</td>

```



```
</body>
</html>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD XHTML 1.0 Transitional//EN"
"http://www.w3.org/TR/xhtml1/DTD/xhtml1-transitional.dtd">
<html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml">
<head>
<LINK href="../_style.css" title="text/css" rel="stylesheet" />
<meta http-equiv="Content-Type" content="text/html; charset=iso-8859-1" />
<title>&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; &#4636;&#4845;&#4621; - &#4853;&#4613;&#4648; -
&#4872;&#4933;</title>
<style type="text/css">
<!--
.style135 {color: #003366; font-size: 9px; font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; }
.style17 {color: #FF0000}
.style20 {font-size: 10px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; }
.style21 {font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif}
.style124 {font-size: 24px; font-weight: bold; color: #006633; }
.style123 {font-size: 12px}
.style136 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; }
.style16 {
    font-size: 10px;
    font-weight: bold;
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif, "Aliens ate my mum", "ESRI
Hydrants", "ESRI Hazardous Materials", "ESRI Geometric Symbols", "ESRI Geology USGS 95-
525", "ESRI Geology AGSO 1", "ESRI Geology", "ESRI Fire Incident NFPA", "ESRI Environmental
& Icons", "ESRI Enviro Hazard Sites", "Eras Bold ITC", "Engravers MT", Elephant, "Edwardian
Script ITC", DS-Digital, "Curlz MT", "Courier New", Courier, "Copperplate Gothic Light",
"Copperplate Gothic Bold", "Cooper Black", Chiller, "Chinese Takeaway", "Colonna MT";
    color: #FF0000;
}
.style138 {
    color: #FFFFFF;
    font-size: 12px;
}
.style143 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #006699; }
.style145 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Tahoma; }
.style146 {
    color: #9ECF40;
    font-family: Geneva, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    font-size: 12px;
}
.style111 {
    font-size: 12px;
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
    color: #006699;
}
.style148 {
    font-size: 9pt;
    font-family: Tahoma;
}
.style153 {font-size: 10px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #006699; }
.style167 {color: #003366; font-size: 9; }
.style168 {font-size: 9; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #003366; }
.style169 {
    font-family: Verdana, Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif;
```

```

        font-size: 9px;
    }
    .style171 {font-size: 7px}
    .style172 {font-size: 9px}
    .style174 {font-size: 12px; font-family: Tahoma; color: #006699;}
    .style178 {color: #FFFFFF}
    .style179 {font-size: 10px; font-family: Arial, Helvetica, sans-serif; color: #FFFFFF;}
    .style182 {font-size: 24px}
    .style183 {
        font-size: 18px;
        color: #003366;
    }
    .style187 {font-size: 18px}
    .style188 {color: #000000; font-family: Tahoma;}
    .style195 {font-size: 14px; font-weight: bold; color: #000000;}
    .style200 {color: #000000}
    .style204 {font-size: 20pt; color: #003366;}
    .style205 {
        font-size: 14px;
        color: #000000;
    }
    .style207 {font-size: 14px}
    .style209 {font-size: 14px; font-weight: bold; color: #003366;}
    .style210 {font-size: 16px}
-->
</style>
<SCRIPT LANGUAGE="JavaScript">
<!-- Original: Jeff Harding (jbh@site-ations.com) -->
<!-- Web Site: http://www.site-ations.com -->

<!-- Day Images (c): http://www.site-ations.com -->
<!-- Month Images (c): http://www.bruce-hamilton.com -->

```

```

<!-- Begin
theDate= new Date();
months = new Array();
days = new Array();
months[1] = "../Images/date-Images/jan.gif";
months[2] = "../Images/date-Images/feb.gif";
months[3] = "../Images/date-Images/mar.gif";
months[4] = "../Images/date-Images/apr.gif";
months[5] = "../Images/date-Images/may.gif";
months[6] = "../Images/date-Images/jun.gif";
months[7] = "../Images/date-Images/jul.gif";
months[8] = "../Images/date-Images/aug.gif";
months[9] = "../Images/date-Images/sep.gif";
months[10] = "../Images/date-Images/oct.gif";
months[11] = "../Images/date-Images/nov.gif";
months[12] = "../Images/date-Images/dec.gif";
days[1] = "../Images/date-Images/1st.gif";
days[2] = "../Images/date-Images/2nd.gif";
days[3] = "../Images/date-Images/3rd.gif";

```



```

        <td width="6%">&nbsp;</td>
        <td width="6%">&nbsp;</td>
        <td width="6%">&nbsp;</td>
        <td width="41%" class="style20 style21 style171">&nbsp;</td>
        <td width="12%" class="style20"><span class="style111 style21"><span
class="style169"></span></span><span class="style183">&#4768;&#4635;&#4653;&#4763</span></td>
        <td width="12%" class="style20"><span class="style20 style21 style172"><span
class="style169"></span></span><span class="style183">&#4725;&#4877;&#4653;&#4763;</span></td>
        <td width="11%" class="style20"><span class="style20 style21 style172"><span
class="style169"></span></span><span class="style183"><a
href="../Oromifa/Index.php">&#4774;&#4654;&#4637;&#4763;</a></span></td>
    </tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></td>
    </tr>
<tr>
    <th width="23%" height="1090" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
        <tr valign="top">
            <th height="83" scope="row"><table width="96%" border="1" align="left"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                <tr>
                    <td height="72"><div align="center">
                        <p><a href="../MAIL/Index.htm" class="menu"><span
class="style204">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; &#4618;&#4757;&#4781;</span></a></p>
                        <p><span class="style183">&#4768;&#4635;&#4653;&#4763</span></p>
                    </div></td>
                </tr>
            </table></th>
        </tr>
        <tr valign="top">
            <th height="1007" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                <tr valign="top">
                    <th height="1007" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                        <tr valign="top">
                            <td width="79%" height="1007"><table width="96%" border="0" align="left"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                                <tr valign="top">
                                    <th height="1003" scope="row"><table width="100%" height="100%"
border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE:
collapse">
                                        <tr>
                                            <th height="129" bgcolor="#F5F6FA" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
                                        </tr>
                                    </tr>
                                <tr>
                                    <th height="35" bgcolor="#D6E6E9" scope="row"><div align="left"><span
class="style145"> &nbsp;</span> <span class="style187">&#4768;&#4661;&#4936;&#4619;&#4874
<span class="style188"> &#4872;&#4934;&#4733;</span></span></div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style20">&nbsp;&nbsp;<span
class="style209">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; &#4636;&#4845;&#4621;</span> <span
class="style209">&#4845;&#4632;&#4829;&#4872;&#4705;</span></div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style20">&nbsp; <span
class="style209">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; &#4661;&#4651;</span> <span
class="style209">&#4845;&#4632;&#4829;&#4872;&#4705;</span></div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style20">&nbsp;Ethiopian Air Lines
</div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style20">&nbsp;Sheraton Addis
</div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style20">&nbsp;Hilton Addis Ababa
</div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style20">&nbsp;Ghion Hotel
</div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style20">&nbsp;Wabe Shebele Hotel
</div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style143" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style20">&nbsp;Ras Hotel
</div></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th height="42" class="style146" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th height="33" bgcolor="#D6E6E9" scope="row"><div align="left"><span
class="style188"> &nbsp;<span class="style187"> &#4710;&#4781;&#4661; ;
&#4774;&#4938;&#4661;</span></span></div>
</th>
</tr>

```

```

        <tr>
            <th class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style167"> 1.
Baby Mama </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style167">2. Super Man </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style167">3. Made
of Honor </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style167">4. Russell Peters Intense Comedy </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style167">5. Hitch
</div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style167">6. Analyze this </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style167">7. The
Recruit </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style168">8. Meet the parent </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left" class="style168">9. Mr
&amp; Mrs Smith </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style20" scope="row"><div align="left"
class="style168">10. Pink Panter </div></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th height="487" bgcolor="#F5F6FA" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
        </tr>
    </table></th>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></th>

```

```

        <td width="77%" class="style135"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr valign="top">
        <th height="1064" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr valign="top">
        <th height="160" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr>
        <th width="44%" height="151"
scope="row"><script>printDate();</script></th>
        <td width="56%"><div align="center">
        <object classid="clsid:D27CDB6E-AE6D-11cf-96B8-444553540000"
codebase="http://download.macromedia.com/pub/shockwave/cabs/flash/swflash.cab#versio
n=7,0,19,0" width="391" height="149" title="animation">
        <param name="movie" value="../Images/animation1.swf" />
        <param name="quality" value="high" />
        <embed src="../Images/animation1.swf" quality="high"
pluginspage="http://www.macromedia.com/go/getflashplayer" type="application/x-
shockwave-flash" width="391" height="149"></embed>
        </object>
        </div></td>
        </tr>
        </table></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
        <th height="39" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
        <th width="35%" height="35" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
        <th width="9%" scope="row"><div align="right"></div></th>
        <td width="86%" bgcolor="#2E99CD"><div align="center"><span
class="style138"><a href="../MAIL/Index.php" class="menu"><span
class="style182">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; :
&#4636;&#4845;&#4621;</span></a></span></div></td>
        <td width="5%"><div align="left"></div></td>
        </tr>
        </table></th>
        <td width="33%"><table width="98%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
        <th width="9%" scope="row"><div align="right"></div></th>
        <td width="86%" bgcolor="#2E99CD"><div align="center"><span
class="style138"><a href="../JOBS/Amharic/Index.php" class="menu"><span
class="style182">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; :
&#4661;&#4651;</span></a></span></div></td>
        <td width="5%"><div align="left"></div></td>
        </tr>
        </table></td>

```



```

&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; : &#4636;&#4845;&#4621; <strong><a href="../MAIL/Index.htm"
class="menu"><span class="style195">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; :</span></a><strong>
&#4661;&#4651;</strong></strong> <a href="../MAIL/Index.htm" class="menu"><span
class="style195">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; : &#4840;&#4622; : &#4872;&#4933; :
</span></a><span class="style200">&#4768;&#4896;&#4675;&#4622; :
&#4840;&#4843;&#4824; : &#4752;&#4813; </span>::</div></th>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th height="487" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
<tr valign="top">
<th width="48%" height="638" scope="row"><table width="98%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
<tr valign="top">
<th height="110" scope="row"><table width="98%" border="1" align="left"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
<tr>
<td height="16" bgcolor="#D6E6E9"><div align="left"
class="style145"> <span
class="style183">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; </span>: <span
class="style183">&#4768;&#4704;&#4707;</span></div></td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
<td height="133"><table width="100%" border="0" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
<tr>
<th width="49%" height="128" scope="row"></th>
<td width="51%"><div align="justify">
<table width="90%" border="0" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
<tr>
<th scope="row"><div align="justify"
class="style209">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; : &#4768;&#4704;&#4707; :
&#4840;&#4770;&#4725;&#4846;&#4917;&#4843; : &#4811;&#4755; :
&#4776;&#4720;&#4635; : &#4661;&#4725;&#4614;&#4757; :
&#4704;&#4813;&#4661;&#4903; &#4840;&#4720;&#4616;&#4843;&#4841; :
&#4840;&#4720;&#4936;&#4901;&#4654; :
&#4632;&#4661;&#4821;&#4710;&#4733;&#4757; &#4840;&#4843;&#4824;&#4733; :
&#4853;&#4611; : &#4776;&#4720;&#4635; : &#4755;&#4725; :: </div> </th>
</tr>
</table>
</div></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
<tr>
<th height="12" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">

```

```

        <th height="306" scope="row"><table width="98%" border="1" align="left"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
            <tr>
                <td bgcolor="#D6E6E9"
class="style145"><div align="left"><span class="style183">&#4632;&#4829;&#4755;&#4763;</span></div></td>
            </tr>
            <tr valign="top">
                <td height="440"><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                    <tr>
                        <th width="48%" height="436" scope="row"><table width="95%"
border="1" align="center" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc"
style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                            <tr>
                                <td><div
align="left">&nbsp; <span
class="style205">&#4633;&#4826;&#4675;</span></div></td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr>
                                <th height="413" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
                            </tr>
                        </table></th>
                        <td width="52%"><table width="95%" border="1" align="center"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                            <tr>
                                <td><div
align="left"> &nbsp; <span
class="style145 style205"><span
class="style207">&#4938;&#4621;&#4637;</span></span></div></td>
                            </tr>
                            <tr valign="top">
                                <th height="414" scope="row"><table width="99%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
                                    <tr>
                                        <th height="38" bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style153"
scope="row"> Russel Peters
Standup commedy </th>
                                        </tr>
                                        <tr>
                                            <th height="122" scope="row"><embed
src="../media/A1Russell Peters.wmv" width="118" height="114"
autostart="false"></embed></th>
                                        </tr>
                                        <tr>
                                            <th bgcolor="#993300" class="style179"
scope="row">download</a></th>
                                        </tr>
                                        <tr>
                                            <th scope="row"><hr /></th>
                                        </tr>
                                        <tr>
                                            <th height="38" bgcolor="#F5F6FA" class="style153"
scope="row"> 24 (Season 7)
Trailer </th>
                    </table>
                </td>
            </tr>
        </table>

```

```

        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th height="122" scope="row"><embed
src="../media/A1Russell Peters.wmv" width="118" height="114"
autostart="False"></embed></th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th bgcolor="#993300" class="style153 style178"
scope="row">download</th>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th height="57" scope="row">&nbsp;</th>
        </tr>
    </table></th>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></th>
<td width="52%"><table width="98%" border="0" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
    <tr valign="top">
        <th height="453" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
            <tr valign="top">
                <td height="213"><table width="100%" height="64%" border="0"
align="center" bordercolor="#a0ce41" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
                    <tr>
                        <td height="18" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style16"><table
width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
                            <tr>
                                <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF"><div align="right"></div></td>
                                <td width="96%" background="../Images/bg.gif"><div
align="left">
                                    <table width="99%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                                        <tr>
                                            <th scope="row"><div align="left"><span
class="style174"></span>
<span
class="style183">&#4635;&#4661;&#4723;&#4808;&#4677;&#4843;</span></div></th>
                                            <td><div align="right"></div></td>
                                        </tr>
                                    </table>
                                </div></td>
                                <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><div
align="left"></div></td>
                            </tr>
                        </table></td>
                    </tr>
                </table></td>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
    </tr>
</table></td>

```



```

        <td><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
            <tr>
                <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
                <td width="40%" class="style20"><span
class="style136">&#4846;&#4755;&#4661; ;
&#4782;&#4637;&#4949;&#4841;&#4720;&#4653;;
&#4635;&#4821;&#4776;&#4621;</span></td>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
        <td><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
            <tr>
                <th width="54%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
                <td width="46%" class="style20"><div
align="justify"><span class="style20 style210">&#4939;&#4757;&#4721; &#4851;&#4710;
&#4708;&#4725</span></div></td>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <th height="64" scope="row"><table width="100%" border="0"
cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
            <tr>
                <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
                <td width="40%" class="style20"><div
align="justify"><span class="style20 style210">&#4939;&#4757;&#4721; &#4851;&#4710;
&#4708;&#4725</span></div></td>
            </tr>
        </table></th>
        <td><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
            <tr>
                <th width="52%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
                <td width="48%" class="style20"><div align="justify"><a
href="../Advertismen.htm" class="menu1"></a><span
class="style209">&#4840;&#4770;&#4725;&#4846;&#4917;&#4843;</span> <span
class="style209">&#4768;&#4840;&#4653; </span><span
class="style209">&#4632;</span><span
class="style209">&#4757;&#4872;&#4853;</span></div></td>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
        <td><table width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
            <tr>
                <th width="60%" scope="row"><div align="left"></div></th>
                <td width="40%" class="style20"><div
align="justify"><span class="style136">&#4846;&#4755;&#4661; ;
&#4782;&#4637;&#4949;&#4841;&#4720;&#4653;;
&#4635;&#4821;&#4776;&#4621;</span></div></td>

```

```

        </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td height="149"><table width="100%" height="64%" border="0"
align="center" bordercolor="#a0ce41" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
    <tr>
        <td height="18" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style16"><table
width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
        <tr>
            <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF"><div align="right"></div></td>
            <td width="96%" background="../../Images/bg.gif"><table
width="99%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
                <tr>
                    <th scope="row"><div align="left"><span
class="style174"><span
class="style138"> <span class="style183">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; ;
&#4636;&#4845;&#4621;</span></span></span></div></th>
                    <td><div align="right"></div></td>
                </tr>
            </table></td>
            <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><div
align="left"></div></td>
        </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>
<tr>
    <td bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style136">&nbsp;</td>
</tr>
<tr valign="top">
    <td height="121" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><table
width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#9ecf40"
style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr valign="top">
            <td height="92"><table width="100%" height="75%"
border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
                <tr>
                    <td width="40%" height="90"><div align="center"><a
href="../../MAIL/Registration.htm"></a></div></td>
                    <td width="4%">&nbsp;</td>
                    <td width="56%"></td>
                </tr>
            </table></td>
        </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>

```

```

        </table></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td><table width="100%" height="64%" border="0" align="center"
bordercolor="#a0ce41" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
            <tr>
                <td height="18" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style16"><table
width="100%" border="0" cellspacing="0" cellpadding="0">
                    <tr>
                        <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF"><div align="right"></div></td>
                        <td width="96%" background="../Images/bg.gif"><div
align="left">
                            <table width="99%" border="0" cellspacing="0"
cellpadding="0">
                                <tr>
                                    <th scope="row"><div align="left"><span
class="style174"><span
class="menu style148"> <span class="style183">&#4768;&#4850;&#4661; ;
&#4661;&#4651;</span></span></span></div></th>
                                    <td><div align="right"></div></td>
                                </tr>
                            </table>
                        </div></td>
                    </tr>
                <td width="2%" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><div
align="left"></div></td>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
    </tr>
    <tr>
        <td bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style136">&nbsp;</td>
    </tr>
    <tr valign="top">
        <td height="77" bgcolor="#FFFFFF" class="style123"><table
width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#9ECF40"
style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
            <tr valign="top">
                <td height="92"><table width="100%" height="75%"
border="0" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0">
                    <tr>
                        <td width="40%" height="90"><div align="center"></div></td>
                        <td width="4%">&nbsp;</td>
                        <td width="56%"></td>
                    </tr>
                </table></td>
            </tr>
        </table></td>
    </tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></th>

```

```

        </tr>
        </table></td>
    </tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
<tr valign="bottom">
    <th height="129" scope="row"><table width="96%" border="1" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr>
            <td height="118"><object classid="clsid:D27CDB6E-AE6D-11cf-96B8-
444553540000"
codebase="http://download.macromedia.com/pub/shockwave/cabs/flash/swflash.cab#versio
n=7,0,19,0" width="829" height="94" title="animation">
                <param name="movie" value="../Images/animation1.swf" />
                <param name="quality" value="high" />
                <embed src="../Images/animation1.swf" quality="high"
pluginspage="http://www.macromedia.com/go/getflashplayer" type="application/x-
shockwave-flash" width="829" height="94"></embed>
            </object></td>
        </tr>
    </table></th>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></td>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
</table></th>
</tr>
<tr valign="top"><td height="21"><table width="98%" border="1" align="center"
cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0" bordercolor="#d2e4fc" bgcolor="#F5F6FA" style="BORDER-
COLLAPSE: collapse">
        <tr>
            <th height="19" scope="row"><span class="style153"> Copyright &copy;Addis Portal . All
Rights Reserved.</span></th>
        </tr>
    </table></td>
</tr>
</table>
</body>
</html>

```

PHP Code

```

<?
                                mysql_connect('127.0.0.1','root','vertrig
o');
                                mysql_select_db('addisjobsenglish');
?>
<?php
include_once("dbAddisJobsEnglish.php");
class AddisJobs{

```

```

function
EmployerRegistration($organization,$contact,$telephone,$email,$username,$password,$altem
ail,$question,$answer)
{
$query="INSERT into employer (organname,
contactname,telephone,email,username,password,altemail,question,securityanswer)
values('$organization','$contact','$telephone','$email','$username','$password','$altemail','$ques
tion','$answer)";
$result=mysql_query($query);
if($result)
echo '<table width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0"
bordercolor="#afc3ea" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
<tr bgcolor="#afc3ea">
  |
```

```

</tr>
</table>';
} //end of employer registration function

function
JobSeekerRegistration($firstname,$secondname,$gender,$country,$username,$password,$altemail,$question,$answer)
{
$query="INSERT into jobseeker (firstname,
secondname,gender,country,username,password,altemail,question,answer)
values('$firstname','$secondname','$gender','$country','$username','$password','$altemail','$question','$answer)";
$result=mysql_query($query);
if($result)
echo '<table width="100%" border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0"
bordercolor="#afc3ea" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
<tr bgcolor="#afc3ea">
 <div style="border: 1px solid #afc3ea; padding: 5px; width: fit-content; margin: auto; text-align: center;"> <img alt="REGISTERED.gif" style="max-height: 50px; max-width: 100px; vertical-align: middle;"/>  <table border="1" align="center" style="border-color:#afc3ea; width:98%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr>  YOUR PROFILE  <img alt="arrarat.JPG" style="max-height: 50px; max-width: 100px; vertical-align: middle;"/> | | | First Name: |  |  Last Name: | | |  |  |

Gender:

  |  |

Country:

  |  |

Username:

  |  |

Password:

  | [Encrypted] |

Alternative E-mail:

  |  |

Security Question:

  |  |

Your Answer:

  |  |

<a href="index.php" style="text-decoration:none; color:#000000;">DONE



```

```

    echo '<table width="90%" border="1" cellpadding="0" cellspacing="0"
bordercolor="#000033" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse">
<tr>
                                <td class="style168"><div
class="style168" align="center">Not Registered! </div></td>
</tr>
</table>';
} //end of job seeker registration function

function verifyUser($username,$password,$tablename)
{
                                $query="select * from
$tablename where username='$username' and password='$password'";

                                $result=mysql_query($query);

$num=mysql_num_rows($result);

                                if($num>0)
                                {
                                                                include
('EmployerMainpage.php');

                                }
                                else
                                                                include
('Index.php');
                                } //end of verifyEmployer function
function
verifyJobseeker($username,$password,$tablename)
{
                                $query="select * from
$tablename where username='$username' and password='$password'";

                                $result=mysql_query($query);

$num=mysql_num_rows($result);

                                if($num>0)
                                {
                                                                include
('JobSeekerMainpage.php');

                                }
                                else
                                                                include
('Index.php');
                                } //end of verifyEmployer function
function UserInformation($query)
{
                                $result=mysql_query($query);
$num=mysql_num_rows($result);
$record=mysql_fetch_array($result);

```

```

                                echo '<span
class="style19"><b>'. $record['organname']. ' Main Page!<br> Currently Accessed by:
'. $record['contactname']. '</b>' ('. $record['email'].')<br>Thanks! <b>';

    //end of UserInformation function
function UserInformationJobseeker($query)
{

                                $result=mysql_query($query);
                                $num=mysql_num_rows($result);
                                $record=mysql_fetch_array($result);
                                echo '<span
class="style19">Welcome <b>'. $record['firstname']. ' '. $record['secondname']. '</b>
( '. $record['username']. ')@addisjobs.com! <b>';

    //end of UserInformation function

function UserInformationTitle($query)
{

                                $result=mysql_query($query);
                                $num=mysql_num_rows($result);
                                $record=mysql_fetch_array($result);
                                echo '<span
class="style36">Welcome To '. $record['organname']. ' Main Page!';

    //end of UserInformation function

function UserInformationTitle2($query)
{

                                $result=mysql_query($query);
                                $num=mysql_num_rows($result);
                                $record=mysql_fetch_array($result);
                                echo '<span class="style7"> Welcome
'. $record['contactname']. ' (<a href="mailto:'. $record['email']. '">'. $record['email']. '</a>');

    //end of UserInformation function
function GenerateVacancyForms($number)
{
    echo'<form action="PostVacancyDetail.php" method="post">

                                <div align="right"><span
class="style202" align="right">Number of Vacancies to be Posted: <input class="style202"
name="txtNumberRecord" value="'. $number. '" type="text" size="1"
readonly="true"/></span></div><br>;

                                for($i=1;$i<=$number;$i++)
                                {

                                        echo'<table width="50%"
align="center" border="1" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse" bordercolor="#afc3ea">
                                        <tr bgcolor="#afc3ea"><td
colspan=2><span class="style202" align="center">VACANCY NUMBER: '. $i.'
                                        </span></td></tr>

```

```

align="Center">
        <tr><td><table width="99%"
                <tr><td><span
class="style143" align="center">Position Title</td><td><input name="textboxp'.$i.'" type="text"
id="txtNumber" /></td></tr>
                <tr><td><span
class="style143" align="center">Description: </td><td><textarea name="textboxd'.$i.'"
rows="5"></textarea></td></tr>
                <tr><td><span
class="style143" align="center">Number of Position: </td><td><input name="textboxn'.$i.'"
type="text" id="txtNumber" /></td></tr>
                <tr><td><span
class="style143" align="center">Contact Person: </td><td><input name="textboxc'.$i.'"
type="text" id="txtNumber" /></td></tr>
                <tr><td><span
class="style143" align="center">P.O.Box</td><td><input name="textboxb'.$i.'" type="text"
id="txtNumber" /></td></tr>
                <tr><td><span
class="style143" align="center">Telephone: </td><td><input name="textboxt'.$i.'" type="text"
id="txtNumber" /></td></tr>
                <tr><td><span
class="style143" align="center">E-mail: </td><td><input name="textboxe'.$i.'" type="text"
id="txtNumber" /></td></tr>
        </table></td></tr></table><br>;
    }/end of for
    echo '<div align="Center"><input
name="Submit" type="submit" class="style38" value="Submit" /></form></div>';

```

}/end of GenerateVacancyForms function

```

function
RegisterVacancies($number,$valuesp,$valuesd,$valuesn,$valuesc,$valuesb,$valuest,$valuee)
{
        $query="INSERT into vacancy
(positiontitle, description,noofposition,contactperson,pobox,telephone,email)
values('$valuesp','$valuesd','$valuesn','$valuesc','$valuesb','$valuest','$valuee')";
        $result=mysql_query($query);
        if($result)
        {
                echo '<table border=1
align="center" style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse" bordercolor="#afc3ea" WIDTH="98%">
                <tr
                bgcolor="#D6E6E9"><td><span class="style143">Position Title</td><td><span
class="style143">Description</td><td><span class="style143">No of Vacant</td><td><span
class="style143">Contact Person</td><td><span class="style143">P.O.Box</td><td><span
class="style143">Telephone</td><td><span class="style143">E-mail</td></tr>
                <tr><td><span class="style7" align="center">'. $valuesp.'</td><td><span class="style7"
align="center">'. $valuesd.'</td><td><span class="style7"
align="center">'. $valuesn.'</td><td><span class="style7"
align="center">'. $valuesc.'</td><td><span class="style7"
align="center">'. $valuesb.'</td><td><span class="style7"
align="center">'. $valuest.'</td><td><span class="style7" align="center">'. $valuee.'</td></tr>

```

```
</table><br>';
```

```
}  
else  
    echo 'not registered';
```

```
}//end of RegisterVacacies Function
```

```
function ViewVacancy()  
{
```

```
    $query="select * from vacancy";  
    $result=mysql_query($query);  
    $num=mysql_num_rows($result);  
    if($result)
```

```
    {  
        for($i=0;$i<$num;$i++)  
        {
```

```
            $record=mysql_fetch_array($result);  
            echo '<br><table
```

```
border="1" width="90%" align="center" bordercolor="#afc3ea" style="border-collapse:collapse">  
            <tr
```

```
bgcolor="#D6E6E9" ><td><span class="style143">Position Title:</span></td><td><span  
class="style7"><b>'. $record['positiontitle'].'</b></span></td></tr>
```

```
            <tr><td><span
```

```
class="style143">Description:</td><td><span  
class="style153">'. $record['description'].'</span></td></tr>
```

```
            <tr
```

```
bgcolor="#F5F6FA"><td><span class="style143">Number of Vacant: </td><td><span  
class="style153">'. $record['noofposition'].'</span></td></tr>
```

```
            <tr><td><span
```

```
class="style143">Contact Person: </td><td><span  
class="style153">'. $record['contactperson'].'</span></td></tr>
```

```
            <tr
```

```
bgcolor="#F5F6FA"><td><span class="style143">P.O.Box: </td><td><span  
class="style153">'. $record['pobox'].'</span></td></tr>
```

```
            <tr><td><span
```

```
class="style143">Telephone: </td><td><span  
class="style153">'. $record['telephone'].'</span></td></tr>
```

```
            <tr
```

```
bgcolor="#F5F6FA"><td><span class="style143">E-mail: </td><td><span class="style153"><a  
href="mailto:'. $record['email'].'">'. $record['email'].'</span></td></tr>
```

```
            </table>';
```

```
        }  
    }  
}
```

```
}//end of if
```

```

} //end of ViewVacancy Function

} //end of class
?>
<?php
include_once("dbYellowpagesEnglish.php");
class BrowseInformation{

function BrowseInfo($tablename,$title)
{

$mysql_query="select * from $tablename";
$result=mysql_query($mysql_query);
$num=mysql_num_rows($result);

if($tablename=="hotels" or
$tablename=="resturant" )// or $tablename="resturant")
{
echo '<table border=1 width=100%
BORDERCOLOR="#ffcc69" STYLE="BORDER-COLLAPSE: COLLAPSE"
ALIGN=CENTER><tr><td><div align=center class="style7" color=BLUE>SEARCH RESULT:
'. $title.'</div></td></tr></table>';

echo '<table border=0 width=80%
align=left border=0 style="BORDER-COLLAPSE:collapse" bordercolor="#EBDB76"><tr><td>';
echo '<br><br><table border=0
width=70% align=center style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse" bordercolor="#EBDB76" >';

if($result)
{
for($i=0;$i<$num;$i++)
{

$record=mysql_fetch_array($result);

echo '<tr><td
rowspan=8 width="40%"><table width="90%" border="1" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
<tr>
<td height="109" "><div align="center"></div></td>
</tr>
</table></td></tr><tr><td rowspan=8
width="2%">&nbsp;</td></tr><tr><td><span class="style43"><a
href="www.'. $record['name'].'.com"
class="menu1">'. $record['name'].'</a></SPAN></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style32">'. $record['description'].'</span></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style32"><b>Subcity: </b>'. $record['subcity'].'</span></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style32"><b>Kebele: </b>'. $record['kebele'].'</span></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style32"><b>Telephone: </b>'. $record['telephone'].'</span></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style16">'. $record['level'].'</span></td></tr><TR
COLSPAN=2><TD>&nbsp;</TD></TR>';

```

```

    }

    //end of if statement

    //end of uper if statement
    else //if($tablename=="bars")
    {
        echo '<table border=1 width=100%
BORDERCOLOR="#ffcc69" STYLE="BORDER-COLLAPSE: COLLAPSE"
ALIGN=CENTER><tr><td><div align=center class="style7" color=BLUE>SEARCH RESULT:
'.$title.'</div></td></tr></table>';

        echo '<table border=0 width=90%
align=left border=0 style="BORDER-COLLAPSE:collapse" bordercolor="#EBDB76"><tr><td>';
        echo '<br><br><table border=0
width=70% align=center style="BORDER-COLLAPSE: collapse" bordercolor="#EBDB76">';

        if($result)
        {
            for($i=0;$i<$num;$i++)
            {

                $record=mysql_fetch_array($result);

                echo '<tr><td
rowspan=8 width="40%"><table width="90%" border="1" align="center" cellpadding="0"
cellspacing="0">
                <tr>
                <td height="109" "><div align="center"></div></td>
                </tr>
                </table></td></tr><tr><td rowspan=8
width="2%">&nbsp;</td></tr><tr><td><span class="style43"><a
href="www.'.$record['name'].'.com"
class="menu1">'.$record['name'].'</a></SPAN></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style32">'.$record['description'].'</span></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style32"><b>Subcity:</b> '.$record['subcity'].'</span></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style32"><b>Kebele: </b>'.$record['kebele'].'</span></td></tr><tr><td><span
class="style32"><b>Telephone: </b>'.$record['telephone'].'</span></td></tr><tr><TR
COLSPAN=2><TD>&nbsp;</TD></TR>';

                //end of if statement

            }

        }

    }

}

//end of BrowseInfo function

```

```
}; //end of BrowseInformation Class  
?>
```

```
<?
```

```
include_once("class.AddisMail.php");  
//session_start();  
$uname=$_POST['txtUsername'];
```

```
$pword=$_POST['txtPassword'];  
$mailVerify=new AddisMail();  
$mailVerify-
```

```
>verifyMailUser($uname,$pword,"member");  
?>
```
